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InBestSoil

Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the

D.4.3 Ex-post forestry impact evaluation report

Universida de Vigo

Ex-post forestry impact assessment report

Summary

The aim of InBestSoil is to collaboratively establish a **framework for investing in the preservation and restoration of soil health**. This includes the creation of an economic valuation system for the ecosystem services provided by healthy soil and the impacts of soil interventions, and its incorporation into business models and incentives. The objective of the project is to enable public and private organizations to assign economic value to their efforts regarding soil health, collaboratively design strategies with local stakeholders, and collectively contribute to achieving national and EU policy objectives. The project implements soil health co-creation and co-design activities using 9 business cases across different biogeographic regions in Europe (Boreal, Continental, Atlantic, Mediterranean) and different land uses (Agriculture, Forest, Urban, Mining).

This report is part of Work Package 4, which focuses on understanding the current innovation processes on soil health interventions and exploring options for upscaling. Specifically, it addresses **T.4.3 Ex-post assessment of forestry business models and** outlines the findings on the impacts generated by the two forestry business cases from the InBestSoil project, Lighthouse 1 (Mediterranean Forestry Soil) and Lighthouse 6 (Boreal Forestry Soil). It demonstrates causal links between prevailing forestry and agroforestry interventions and observed impacts, particularly in terms of land management, soil health and socio-economic dimensions.

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Contents

1.	Executive Summary.....	6
2.	Introduction	8
2.1.	Connection to the Mission Soil and EU Forestry Strategy.....	9
3.	Methodology: Ex-post assessment of forestry business models.....	10
3.1.	Desk research.....	11
3.2.	Qualitative approach to the ex-post forestry impact assessment.....	11
3.2.1.	Interview methodology & guidelines.....	11
3.2.2.	Assessment tool.....	13
3.2.3.	Stakeholder selection.....	14
3.3.	Data collection	14
3.3.1.	Data analysis methodology	14
3.3.2.	Data protection	14
4.	Lighthouse 1: Spanish agroforest.....	16
4.1.	Description and interventions of Lighthouse 1.....	18
4.1.1.	Lighthouse 1 business model.....	21
4.1.2.	Lighthouse 1 agroforestry interventions related to soil health.....	24
4.2.	Drivers and barriers to implement soil health practices in Lighthouse 1	25
4.3.	Ex-post agroforestry impact assessment.....	27
4.4.	Relation to soil health indicators for lighthouse 1.....	29
5.	Lighthouse 6: Latvian forest.....	30
5.1.	Description and interventions of Lighthouse 6.....	32
5.1.1.	Lighthouse 6 business model.....	34
5.1.2.	Lighthouse 6 forestry interventions related to soil health.....	37
5.2.	Drivers and barriers to implement soil health practices in Lighthouse 6.....	39
5.3.	Ex-post forestry impact assessment	41
5.4.	Relation to soil health indicators for lighthouse 6.....	43
6.	Discussion.....	45
6.1.	Comparative analysis and key takeaways	45
6.2.	Carbon credits.....	49
6.2.1.	Carbon credit market analysis to LH1.....	50
6.2.2.	Carbon credit market analysis to LH6.....	52
6.2.3.	Vision for the future of the carbon credit market	53
7.	Conclusion.....	55
8.	Annex.....	56
8.1.	Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide	56
8.2.	Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide – Spanish version	64

8.3.	Consent form.....	72
8.4.	Drivers and Barriers to implementing soil health related forestry practices - synthesis.....	75
8.4.1.	Drivers and barriers to LH1.....	75
8.4.2.	Drivers and barriers to LH6.....	76
8.5.	Ex-post forestry impact assessments - synthesis.....	79
8.5.1.	LH1 ex-post agroforestry impact assessment.....	79
8.5.2.	LH6 ex-post forestry impact assessment.....	80
9.	References.....	83

List of Figures

Fig.1:	Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide	12
Fig.2:	Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool	13
Fig.3:	LH1 landscape	17
Fig.4:	LH1 forestry activities.....	24
Fig.5:	Ex-post agroforestry impact assessment tool LH1.....	28
Fig.8:	LH6 landscape	31
Fig.7:	LH6 forestry activities.....	37
Fig.8:	Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool LH6.....	42
Fig.9:	Carbon credit market mechanism.....	49

List of Tables

Table 1:	LH1 overview (from D2.2)	16
Table 2:	Most sensitive soil health indicators for LH1.....	18
Table 3:	Stakeholders interviewed for LH1.....	20
Table 4:	Regenerative agroforestry business model framework for LH1.....	23
Table 5:	Drivers and barriers to implementing soil health practices in LH1	26
Table 6:	Linking observed impacts to soil health indicators for LH6.....	29
Table 7:	LH6 overview (from D2.2)	30
Table 8:	Most sensitive soil health indicators for LH6.....	32
Table 9:	Stakeholders interviewed for LH6.....	33
Table 10:	Research-driven forestry business model framework for LH6	36
Table 11:	Drivers and barriers to implementing soil health practices in LH6	40
Table 12:	Linking observed impacts to soil health indicators for LH6.....	44
Table 13:	Comparative analysis LH1 & LH6	45
Table 14:	Sustainable forestry business model – key takeaways.....	48

List of Abbreviations

abbreviation	Meaning
LH	Lighthouse
SHP	Soil Health Practices
SBM	Sustainable Business Model
EOV	Ecological Outcome Verification
HNV	High Nature Value

1. Executive Summary

This report presents an ex-post assessment of the impacts of forestry practices in two experimental sites, Lighthouse 1 (LH1) in Spain and Lighthouse 6 (LH6) in Latvia. The study examines how land and forest management strategies influence soil health, biodiversity, carbon sequestration and socio-economic dynamics. The assessment identifies key drivers, barriers and takeaways to implement resilient forestry practices.

This report is primarily intended for foresters, land managers, researchers, policymakers, and practitioners involved in sustainable land-use planning, environmental monitoring, and soil health policy development. Specifically, it supports national and EU-level actors working to implement sustainable forest and soil conservation strategies in managed forest systems, particularly those addressing critical soil health challenges such as erosion, drought, land degradation, and nutrient loss.

The assessment focuses on two contrasting forestry sites: LH1, a silvopastoral agroforestry landscape shaped by farmer-led innovation, and LH6, a boreal research forest centred on scientific experimentation and monitoring. The study was conducted using semi-structured interviews with local land managers, researchers, and representatives from public institutions.

The methodology included qualitative and comparative assessments in terms of business model, intervention strategies, barriers and drivers to implementation, and broader societal, economic and environmental impact. Special attention was given to identify the contribution of observed outcomes such as soil health, biodiversity, community impact and profitability.

The report includes the following key results:

- **Result 1: ex-post forestry assessment interview guide**

A structured interview guide was developed to assess forestry practices across the experimental sites. This guide enables consistent data collection, providing a replicable tool for future assessments and cross-site comparison. The guide is available in English and Spanish.

- **Result 2: sustainable business model frameworks**

Tailored business model frameworks were developed for both LH1 and LH6 to capture how each site operates. These include the *Regenerative agroforestry business model framework* connected to LH1 and the *Research-driven forestry business model framework* connected to LH6. These frameworks help identify revenue opportunities, key actors, and activities that support soil health, offering replicable models for sustainable forest management across different contexts. Key takeaways of these business models are combined in a *Sustainable forestry business model*.

- **Result 3: ex-post forestry impact assessment tool**

The impact assessment tool helps assess the social, economic, environmental and institutional/legal impacts of various forestry and agroforestry interventions and soil health practices across the LHs. This tool links specific practices to outcomes supporting evidence-based decision-making and guiding future land management strategies.

The findings emphasize the value of multi-actor collaboration, adaptive management, and context-driven approaches in forestry. For forest practitioners, both LH1 and LH6 provide replicable elements: LH1 showcases farmer-driven ecological practices; LH6 exemplifies how experimental monitoring, and public-sector engagement can shape national standards.

For policymakers at the national and EU level, this assessment underscores the need for integrated soil health business model frameworks that support both bottom-up (LH1) and top-down (LH6) pathways. Incentives for diversified revenue streams, support for research, practice collaborations, and alignment with Mission Soil objectives, especially soil structure, organic matter, and erosion reduction, are essential. Policy instruments should accommodate varied ownership models, from family-run farms to public research forests.

This ex-post forestry impact assessment highlights how soil health goals can be embedded into forest systems through diverse strategies and stakeholder collaboration. The ex-post assessment interview guide, business model frameworks and impact assessment tool provide valuable tools for assessing and designing resilient forestry models across Europe. These insights will inform future projects, contribute to Mission Soil objectives and the EU Forest Strategy for 2030, and guide the development of scalable sustainable forest interventions for soil and ecosystem restoration.

Deliverable Results

The deliverable is divided in two main sections: the analysis of LH1 and LH6. In order to provide an easy overview of the main outcomes, we provide direct access to the main results and tools of this deliverable.

Methodology results:

- [Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide](#)
- [Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool](#)

Lighthouse 1 results:

- [Regenerative agroforestry business model framework for LH1](#)
- [Ex-post agroforestry impact assessment tool LH1](#)

Lighthouse 6 results:

- [Research-driven forestry business model framework for LH6](#)
- [Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool LH6](#)

Combined results:

- [Sustainable forestry business model – key takeaways](#)

2. Introduction

InBestSoil is a Horizon Europe-funded project that addresses the urgent and growing global challenge of soil degradation, including erosion, compaction, and declining fertility. The core objective of InBestSoil is to co-create a framework that enables investment in soil health by making the benefits of soil conservation and restoration more visible, measurable, and economically valued. By assessing the real-world impact of soil health interventions across a diverse set of land uses, the project aims to support the development of sustainable business models that incentivize both private and public actors to adopt sustainable practices.

This report forms part of **Work Package 4, which focuses on identifying, assessing, and upscaling innovative soil health interventions**. WP4 examines a variety of real-life business cases to assess their outcomes and potential for broader replication. The ultimate goal is to transform these local examples into scalable, economically viable models that can help mainstream sustainable land management across Europe.

Within this context, **Deliverable 4.3 presents an ex-post impact assessment** of two InBestSoil forestry case studies:

- Lighthouse 1 (LH1), located in Extremadura, Spain, represents a Mediterranean agroforestry system where forest soil quality has been improved through rotational grazing practices involving livestock species (mainly cattle and sheep). The farmers interviewed for LH1 began implementing these practices at different times, some more than 10 years ago, while others started less than 5 years ago.
- Lighthouse 6 (LH6), based in Latvia, operates within a Boreal Forest context. It focuses on improving soil quality through several approaches, including the recirculation of nutrients (e.g., wood ash), species selection, tree breeding, and sustainable forest management. Key practices include selecting appropriate soil and planting spot preparation methods based on landscape features (e.g., terrain slope) and soil fertility, regulating the water table, and restoring forest ecosystems on former mining sites.

These case studies offer valuable insights into how forest and agroforestry systems can support soil health, contribute to ecosystem restoration, and generate benefits in terms of biodiversity, climate resilience, and rural economic development. The ex-post impact assessment investigates the effects of forestry activities in LH1 and LH2, addressing the central research question: *What has been the social, environmental, economic and institutional impact of forestry interventions in these sites?* The assessment report also aims to provide sustainable business model frameworks and ex-post forestry impact assessment tools that are easily scalable and usable by other forest cases. While this assessment follows a qualitative approach based on stakeholder value perceptions and observed outcomes, the findings can be interpreted through established soil health indicators linked to ecosystem services of WP3. The findings of this deliverable feed directly into the objectives of both the Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' and the EU Forest Strategy for 2030, as outlined in the following section.

2.1. Connection to the Mission Soil and EU Forestry Strategy

This deliverable forms part of the InBestSoil project, which is funded under the European Union's Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'. The mission's overarching goal is to raise awareness, share knowledge, and promote sustainable soil management practices that contribute to the conservation and restoration of soil health across Europe. While focused primarily on soils, the Mission is closely aligned with broader EU environmental and climate targets, including those laid out in the EU Forest Strategy for 2030, given the vital role forests play in soil protection, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity preservation.

InBestSoil includes nine study areas (including Lighthouses and Living labs) spanning four biogeographic regions. Two of these focus specifically on forestry and agroforestry systems. This report provides an ex-post impact assessment of these two forestry business cases, assessing the effectiveness of management practices in promoting sustainable forest use, enhancing soil health, and delivering broader ecosystem services.

The EU Forest Strategy for 2030, adopted on 14 July 2021, is a core pillar of the European Green Deal and contributes to the EU's ambition to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030. The strategy aims to increase forest resilience to climate change, restore forest ecosystems, and expand forest coverage and biodiversity across Europe. It promotes sustainable forest management (SFM), supports forest-based industries, including innovative alternatives like ecotourism and non-wood products, and introduces financial incentives for climate-friendly practices such as carbon storage.

This deliverable contributes directly to the objectives of both the Soil Mission and the Forest Strategy by:

- Providing evidence-based insights into how forest sites implement management practices that enhance soil structure, conserve forest biodiversity, and restore degraded ecosystems, while continuing their commercial operations
- Assessing the impact of real-world forestry and agroforestry business cases that serve as replicable models of good practice
- Providing sustainable business model frameworks and ex-post forestry impact assessment tool, that enable the assessment of forestry interventions on soil health, offering practical, replicable approaches for application in other forest projects
- Offering key takeaways and lessons that can inform future forestry land-use and soil-health interventions across Europe

In doing so, the report helps bridge the knowledge gap between soil health and forestry practices and strengthens the case for sustainable land management.

3. Methodology: Ex-post assessment of forestry business models

To assess the impact of forestry interventions, a qualitative research approach was applied. The study involved both online and in-person interviews with local stakeholders at the LH1 (Spain) and LH6 (Latvia) sites. A qualitative method was chosen because soil health projects and soil health practices adoption rely heavily on stakeholder engagement, and interviews allow for capturing local perspectives, experiences, and priorities.

In-person interviews also enabled site visits, which provided additional context and a deeper understanding of the forestry settings. This combination of interviews and site observations helped to place stakeholder views within the broader environmental and management context.

The analysis was guided by the sustainable business model (SBM) framework, which examines how organizations create value by integrating social, environmental, and economic factors (Karuppiyah, Sankaranarayanan, & Mithun, 2023). Previous research has shown the relevance of SBMs in forestry contexts, specifically studying the drivers, challenges and long-term sustainability transitions (Benjaminsson, Kronholm, & Erlandsson, 2019). The study showcases that a BMC with key questions in each component is a practical way to research forestry business models (Benjaminsson, Kronholm, & Erlandsson, 2019). In this study, a similar methodology was used and included analyzing the application of sustainable business models within each Lighthouse site, assessing their impact, and exploring ways to future-proof, replicate, and scale these models in other forestry-related contexts. A qualitative assessment was prioritized to capture the relationships stakeholders perceive between forestry practices and their impacts.

Building on earlier qualitative research exploring environmental and socio-economic indicators (Luhás & Mikkilá, 2024) this study examines local stakeholders' perceptions of soil health and the resulting impacts on their business models.

The methodology was presented to FiBL, the Work Package 4 lead, and other task contributors, ensuring alignment with related tasks and enhancing overall coherence within the work package. This deliverable builds on the work presented in deliverable D4.1, which summarized various sustainable business model archetypes as well as key drivers and barriers to implementing soil health practices (SHP). The business models developed in D4.1 serve as overarching frameworks and practical options for professionals seeking to integrate SHP into their agricultural systems. In contrast to D4.1's focus on archetypes, D4.3 examines the full business operations of the LH1 and LH6. It offers operational guidance and hands-on examples of how foresters are implementing regenerative practices to enhance their forest ecosystems while simultaneously strengthening their commercial activities.

To further support the interpretation of qualitative findings, reference was made to established soil health indicators linked to ecosystem services of WP3. These soil health indicators for LH1 and LH6 are used as an interpretative framework to relate observed impacts to recognized soil health dimensions.

3.1. Desk research

The first step in this impact study involved developing a comprehensive understanding of the contexts surrounding the Latvian and Spanish forest sites. This included examining landscape features, forestry characteristics, climatic conditions, and the nature of local forestry interventions. Deliverables D2.1 and D2.2 linked to WP2, the *identification and mapping of stakeholders for each site*, led by Zabala, were instrumental in gaining a better understanding of each site. These deliverables already provided a detailed analysis of the specific characteristics, and conditions of the Lighthouses areas.

To further support the desk research of LH1 and LH6, LGI obtained relevant documentation from the Lighthouses site coordinators, [Fundación Global Nature](#) and [ACTYVA](#) for the Spanish site, and [SILAVA](#) for the Latvian forests. The resources, including articles and reports, offered deeper insights into the local forestry practices. This background research offered a strong foundation for understanding each stakeholder's role, specialization, and involvement in the Lighthouses initiatives, while also helping to identify key questions and topics to explore further, thereby supporting the development of the interview guide and enhancing the overall interview process.

3.2. Qualitative approach to the ex-post forestry impact assessment

3.2.1. Interview methodology & guidelines

This study employed a semi-structured interview approach, allowing for a balance between consistency across interviews and flexibility to explore stakeholder-specific knowledge. An interview guide was developed based on insights from the initial desk research. This guide helped structure the conversation around key themes while providing space to ask follow-up questions tailored to each stakeholder's expertise and interests. The interview guide, represented in Figure 1, covered a range of topics related to forestry and soil health. The main sections included:

Fig.1: Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide

The full interview guide is provided in Annex 8.1 and serves as a framework for the ex-post assessment of forestry sites. As one of the key outcomes of this study, the guide is designed to be accessible and adaptable, offering a useful resource for other projects conducting similar research. To ensure accessibility and effective communication, the guide was translated into Spanish for interviews conducted at the Spanish forestry site. The Spanish interview guide is provided in Annex 8.2. Interviews at the Latvian forestry site were conducted in English.

3.2.2. Assessment tool

To evaluate the impact of forestry and agroforestry activities, we developed an assessment model based on the questions from the interview guide: the **Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool**, see figure 2. This model helps assess how forest management objectives translate into specific practices and how these practices relate to environmental, social, economic, and institutional impacts. Designed as a replicable tool, it can be applied to other pilot sites and/or adapted beyond forestry contexts to support different types of research. Once completed, the tool supports evidence-based decision-making and aims to inspire foresters, researchers, and land managers to adopt practices that improve soil structure and enhance ecosystem resilience. The ex-post forestry impact assessment tool is one of the key outcomes of this study.

Fig.2: Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool

3.2.3. Stakeholder selection

Stakeholders were identified through collaboration with the Lighthouses site coordinators, who maintain direct connections with local forestry networks. Selection was based on the stakeholders' active roles in the management, research, or operations of the forestry sites. Their participation was essential, as they provided valuable insights into local forestry interventions, challenges, and impacts.

Initial contact with stakeholders was made by the site coordinators, who introduced the study and extended the interview invitations. Most interviews were conducted in person, enabling meaningful dialogue and on-site visits. LH6 interviews were held in Riga, Salaspils and Jelgava (Latvia) on June 3–4, 2024, while LH1 interviews took place in Cáceres (Spain) on November 26, 2023, and online on December 18, 2024, and March 12, 2025. This direct engagement provided valuable insight into the landscape and deepened understanding of both Lighthouse contexts. In total, five stakeholders from the Latvian forestry site and four from the Spanish agroforestry site were interviewed; two of the Spanish interviews were conducted online due to logistical constraints.

3.3. Data collection

3.3.1. Data analysis methodology

To ensure accuracy and completeness, all semi-structured interviews were audio-recorded. This approach allowed the interviewer to be fully engaged in the conversation, focusing on active and dynamic listening, rather than solely focusing on extensive notetaking. The recorded interviews served as the primary data source, capturing detailed insights into each stakeholder's role, experiences, and perspectives. Stakeholders represented a diverse range of involvement, including land managers, researchers, and forestry practitioners. The structured interview guide facilitated the collection of consistent data across all interviews, enabling thematic alignment and easier comparison across sites. Following the interviews, the audio recordings were used to take additional notes and identify recurring topics, patterns, and key themes across the interviews. Insights from individual interviews were synthesized and translated into a single consolidated business model for each LH. These aggregated models brought together diverse perspectives into a coherent storyline, supporting a structured assessment of each LH's outcomes and contextual dynamics. No complete transcription was made of the interviews, due to limited time availability and the length of the interviews.

3.3.2. Data protection

Prior to each interview, participants received an informed consent form outlining the purpose of the study, the intended use of the data, and their rights regarding participation and privacy. Consent of each stakeholder was obtained to record the interviews. The recordings were used solely to support the data analysis and ensure the accuracy of data interpretation. After the analysis phase and the completion of the study, all recordings were securely deleted. All participants provided explicit consent to be identified in the study. As such, their names and

roles may be included where relevant. If necessary, the consent form was translated into the local language of the participants. The English version of the consent form for this study can be found in annex 8.3.

4. Lighthouse 1: Spanish agroforest

LH1 refers to the Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván, an experimental site representing the Mediterranean forestry soil. El Baldío de Talaván is situated between the Mediterranean mountain range of Monfragüe and the Llanos de Cáceres. The site is coordinated by Fundación Global Nature and Actyva Cooperativa.

The term 'Dehesa' describes a traditional silvopastoral system that integrates livestock farming, agriculture, and forestry. The land is characterized by scattered trees growing over grassland which is used for grazing livestock including pigs, cattle and sheep.

The area has evolved into a space where collaborative efforts, combining livestock farming, agriculture, and nature conservation, coexist to support sustainable business models. Practices such as rotational grazing and holistic land management contribute to improved forestry outcomes and enhanced soil conservation.

Given its Mediterranean context, El Baldío is subject to extreme weather conditions, characterized by high temperatures and low rainfall. These climatic stresses significantly affect the soil, leading to reduced vegetation cover, a poorer habitat for microorganisms, and progressive soil degradation. Table

1, showcases an overview of LH1. Figure 3 further provides pictures taken during the LH1 field visit while interviewing stakeholders.

Table 1: LH1 overview (from D2.2)

LH Coordinator partner	Fundación Global Nature & Actyva Cooperativa
LH name (location)	Dehesa El Baldío de Talaván
Region	Talaván (Cáceres), Extremadura
Country	Spain
Area (Ha)	5.94 ha of best conditions (total area 232ha)
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No vegetative growth all year round • No humidity and temperature conditions for the necessary microbiological activity • Continuous degradation

Fig.3: LH1 landscape

The context of the Dehesa is further reflected through key soil health indicators identified in WP3 that characterize the Dehesa system. The combination of low and variable vegetation cover, high land surface temperatures, and water scarcity, captured by indicators such as NDVI, vegetation cover, and land surface temperature, illustrates the climatic pressures shaping productivity in this landscape. At the same time, indicators of soil organic carbon and microbial biodiversity point to an underlying ecological potential, in which soils retain the capacity to support diverse biological activity, with relatively high organic matter content contributing to nutrient availability for plants and microorganisms. Structural indicators such as bulk density further reflect the importance of maintaining soil porosity and water infiltration in these dry conditions. Together, these indicators help frame the Dehesa as a fragile yet responsive system, where management practices play a critical role in balancing the risks of degradation with opportunities for regeneration. Table 2 provides an overview of the soil health indicators assessed in WP3 on the economic valuation of ecosystem services and qualitative impacts of soil interventions for LH1. While this study does not present quantitative values, these indicators offer important context for understanding the soil conditions of the Dehesa.

Table 2: Most sensitive soil health indicators for LH1

Category ES	Soil Ecosystem Services	Soil health indicators
Provisioning	Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) & Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST)
Regulating	Erosion control	Vegetation cover
	Nutrient cycling	Available phosphorus, Exchangeable magnesium & Available phosphorus
	Flood regulation and water storage	Bulk density, Water content at field capacity
	Climate regulation	Total organic carbon
Supporting	Habitat for organisms (landscape heterogeneity)	Soil sealing
	Biodiversity	Fungal Chao1 index, Fungal Shannon Index & Total PLFAs

4.1. Description and interventions of Lighthouse 1

Lighthouse 1 (LH1) is composed of a network of agroforestry areas and farms situated within the Dehesa landscape, managed by a diverse group of farmers, livestock producers, and land managers. Much of the land is family-owned and has been passed down through generations, often undergoing ownership transitions through inheritance. This generational shift has opened the door to younger farmers who are increasingly focused on innovative, sustainable practices. Farmers interviewed in la Dehesa are moving away from conventional livestock farming in favour of regenerative and rotational grazing systems, commonly referred to as holistic land management. These practices aim to integrate livestock and trees to enhance soil health, mitigate soil degradation, and foster biodiversity. The stakeholders interviewed for this study are central to LH1 and form an integral part of the local ecosystem, working to improve Dehesa land management.

Definition <i>Holistic Management</i> By Savory Institute	Holistic Management uses a decision-making process to help ensure that the actions taken to restore land and livelihoods are ecologically, socially and economically sound based on the context described by the people involved. (Savory Institute, 2020)
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While the land characteristics and management profiles of each interviewed farmer differ, this analysis focuses on the shared implementation of holistic management practices across their farms. We conducted interviews with four farmers who, while not fully representative of the broader farming population in La Dehesa which constitutes over 3.5 Million hectares of farmland, offer valuable

insights. Their experiences and practices can serve as inspiration for others in the region seeking to adopt more sustainable and innovative land management approaches. Table 3 offers a concise overview of each land manager interviewed and highlights key characteristics of their respective sites.

Table 3: Stakeholders interviewed for LH1

LH1 stakeholders interviewed			
Name	Role description	Agroforest location & size	Animal production & Forest species
Manuel Die Dean	<p>Manager of a family-owned company '<i>Agrícola Bove</i>'. Livestock producer and farm manager.</p> <p>Practices regenerative agriculture and holistic land management, with a focus on techniques such as rotational grazing.</p>	<p>Elvas, Portugal 500 hectares & Campo Maior, Portugal 200 hectares</p>	<p>300 cows Holm Oaks, Olive groves,</p>
Pia Sánchez	<p>Organic sheep farmer and founder and president of Fedhesa (Federación Estatal de Dehesas).</p> <p>Key leadership role in promoting sustainable silvopastoral practices, advocating for policy support, and representing the interests of Dehesa land managers at the national level.</p>	<p>Merida, Badajoz 440 hectares</p>	<p>400 white and black Merino sheep. Holm and Cork oaks trees</p>
Alfredo Alejandro Fernandez Stimper	<p>Manages a cattle farm, with a focus on improving conventional livestock practices.</p> <p>Actively seeks more cost-effective and sustainable management strategies, with a particular interest in how livestock can contribute to soil conservation through methods such as rotational grazing and regenerative land use.</p>	<p>Casas de Millán, Cáceres 350 hectares</p>	<p>120 cows and 6 bulls Holm Oaks, Resprouts</p>
Beatriz de Pablos	<p>Livestock manager of a family-owned cattle ranch farm called '<i>Ganadería Pablos</i>'.</p> <p>Transforms traditional working methods of livestock farming with sustainable innovative methods.</p>	<p>Trujilo, Cáceres 400 hectares</p>	<p>Cattle: 180 cows, 8 bulls, 100 calves Holm Oak, Olive groves, broom shrubs</p>

4.1.1. Lighthouse 1 business model

Table 4 presents the combined business model for LH 1, reflecting a synthesis of insights gathered from the four farmers engaged in holistic management across the Dehesa landscape. This model does not represent a single farm but rather a collective approach shaped through peer exchange, experimentation, and a shared vision for regenerative land use. The model serves as a **Sustainable business model framework for regenerative agroforestry**, an adaptive tool that can inspire agroforestry sites with a silvopastoral system.

Despite differences in livestock types, scales, and products (e.g., meat, wool, olive oil), these farms share common agroforestry and silvopastoral practices aimed at improving soil health, biodiversity, and ecosystem resilience. In the challenging Dehesa environment, marked by dry conditions and shallow, rocky soils, these farmers show that regenerative practices can successfully restore degraded land and sustain production.

While the regenerative practices and their impacts will be explored in greater detail in the following sections, this model already provides a clear illustration of how regenerative approaches are implemented within farm operations.

Key value proposition

The value proposition of LH1 centres on producing high-quality, nature-based goods, including grass-fed meat, olive oil, and wool, while actively contributing to the ecological regeneration of the Dehesa landscape. This regenerative approach not only sustains production but also opens opportunities to enter the carbon and biodiversity credit markets. Moreover, the success and visibility of these practices have positioned LH1 as an emerging knowledge hub for sustainable land management in the region.

Key partnerships

A critical enabler of this transformation is the robust network of collaboration and support that underpins these practices. Initiatives like AleJAB (*Asociación Juntas Arreglamos la Biosfera*), a non-profit network of agricultural change-makers, are central in helping farmers transition to regenerative methods. As a regional knowledge-sharing platform, AleJAB plays a pivotal role in peer-to-peer education, co-creation of solutions, and ongoing mutual support. AleJAB is part of the Savory Institute, an international non-profit organization committed to the regeneration of grasslands through Holistic Management. The Savory Institute has played a key role in transferring the insights and practices developed in Zimbabwe, where Holistic Management was first pioneered, to land management systems in the United States and Europe. These organisations, along with academic institutions and collaborative European initiatives, have opened doors to structured training programs, broader exposure, and validation of regenerative methods. Notably, the [LIFE Project Live-Adapt \(LIFE17 CCA/ES/000035\)](#) has supported farmers in Mediterranean silvopastoral systems by promoting practical, scalable models of regenerative land use. Together, these networks strengthen the Dehesa farming community, fostering a culture of experimentation, resilience, and continuous learning.

Key beneficiaries / customers

Given the diverse production systems found on Dehesa farms, the business model serves a wide range of customers. These include the agri-food and textile industries, which purchase meat, olive oil, and wool, as well as institutional and cultural buyers, such as museums. In addition, fellow farmers, activists, and sustainability-minded practitioners engage with training and consulting services offered by some farmers pioneering regenerative practices.

Governance

Farms are primarily family-managed, ensuring a close connection to the land. This governance structure is complemented by regional networks and federations that empower farmers with a stronger collective voice in local governance. For example, the Spanish Dehesa Federation brings together farmers to help shape national policy, raising awareness and contributing to the development of legislation that supports the proper management of the Dehesa landscape.

Key resources & services

The holistic management model requires key infrastructure resources like fencing and water access for rotational grazing. More crucial are human resources, the knowledge, motivation, and peer networks that enable consistent application of holistic management. Services provided include training in holistic management and participation in EU or national initiatives to further support skill development and innovation.

Cost structure & revenue streams

Next to more straightforward operational and equipment costs, farmers might also incur expenses related to data sampling and soil monitoring. On the revenue side, farmers benefit from sales of products (meat, wool, olive oil, live animals), which have increased alongside higher yields. Additional income is also generated through training services, and possible awards or recognition for regenerative practices. LH1 coordinators also noted that a rational grazing eco-scheme is planned for implementation in Extremadura; however, detailed information on the initiative remains limited at this stage. Moreover, the interviewed farmers also participate in national projects in which the costs of monitoring and grazing-planning advice are covered as needed, along with potential support for field investments.

One notable market shift is the growing interest among farmers interviewed in carbon credits as a potential revenue stream. While this opportunity is reflected in the business model, most have not yet realized substantial income from it. Although enthusiasm is rising, concrete mechanisms for implementation are still underdeveloped. A more detailed analysis of the potential and current limitations of carbon credit schemes will be provided later in the paper.

By consolidating the diverse experiences and strategies of these farmers into one business model, we capture not only the mechanics of regenerative agroforestry but also the values of collaboration. This combined model serves as a replicable and adaptive framework for sustainable land stewardship under adverse climatic and environmental conditions.

Table 4: Regenerative agroforestry business model framework for LH1

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value propositions	Key beneficiaries / Customers	Governance
<p>AleJAB – Central regional network; farmers mentioned involvement, with peer-led training and knowledge exchange</p> <p>Savory Institute & Complutense University of Madrid – Institutional support for regenerative agriculture, including online holistic management training</p> <p>Project LIFE – Project to promote and scale-up regenerative farming</p> <p>BBVA & El Celler de Can Roca – Provided national recognition (best sustainable producer in 2024)</p> <p>Wooldreamers Project – Commercial partner for wool sales</p> <p>MoMA Museum – Cultural validation of wool sustainability via exhibition</p> <p>Carbon Farmers / Carbon+ – Monetization through carbon credits (still in the development process)</p> <p>Fundacion Global Nature & Actyva cooperative – LH1 coordinators for InBestSoil</p>	<p>Agroforestry integration – Grazing animals under trees, potentially combining oil and animal production while improving soil fertility</p> <p>Holistic, regenerative, and rotational grazing – Core across all farms; includes grazing with long recovery breaks</p> <p>Grass finishing – Animals fed exclusively on pasture for better meat quality and ecosystem health</p> <p>Education and training delivery – Formal and informal programs on sustainable livestock management</p> <p>No use of pesticides and animal produce unless clinical need</p>	<p>Ecological regeneration:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing soil, trees, and biodiversity through grazing Rural economic revitalization <p>Premium product diversity:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grass-fed beef, calves, lamb Organic wool Olive oil Dairy produce Honey <p>Carbon sequestration and ecosystem services</p> <p>Knowledge-based services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Courses and practical training in holistic management. 	<p>Agri-food and textile industries – Meat, oil, wool buyers</p> <p>Sustainability/quality-minded consumers – Direct meat buyers</p> <p>Institutional buyers – Museums, cultural partners</p> <p>Fellow farmers – Buying cows for fattening and/or use training services for holistic management</p> <p>European and public initiatives – Funders and collaborators</p>	<p>Family-managed farms – Operational core is typically within the family</p> <p>Federated roles and regional representation – E.g. participation in the Spanish Dehesa Federation</p> <p>Collaborative networks – Especially AleJAB for education and farmer-led innovation</p>
		Key resources	Key Services	
		<p>Basic equipment – Farms use very minimal infrastructure & equipment for rotational grazing is minimal</p> <p>Human resources – Training capacity, knowledge & interest to learn</p> <p>Network of farmers – peer-learning holistic management</p>	<p>Training and consulting:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Holistic management Rotational grazing Climate adaptation in livestock <p>Participation in EU and national projects</p> <p>Possible carbon credit certification and sales</p>	
		Cost structure	Revenue streams	
		<p>Operation costs: animal care, planning, land management</p> <p>Equipment costs: equipment for grazing and fencing infrastructure</p> <p>Costs related to soil monitoring</p> <p>Costs related to training modules followed</p>	<p>Direct product sales:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Grass-fed beef and lamb Conventional meat sales Wool Olive oil Live animals (calves, cows) <p>Training and services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Course fees and advisory services on holistic practices <p>Carbon credits (in development)</p> <p>Awards and recognition – Monetary and prestige value</p> <p>European and public incentives – CAP (though specific holistic management support is still limited)</p> <p>European project funding –EU projects</p> <p>National project funding – PASTURE+, POCTEP</p>	

4.1.2. Lighthouse 1 agroforestry interventions related to soil health

Farmers across the Dehesa region are implementing a range of agroecological interventions that form the foundation of their regenerative agroforestry systems and are grounded in their holistic management principles.

In the Dehesa region, farmers integrate their animals into tree-based systems, such as grazing sheep or calves beneath olive trees. This form of **silvopastoralism** promotes multiple ecosystem services, providing shade for animals while improving the soil nutrition. This system exemplifies the multifunctional nature of agroforestry, where animal health, biodiversity, and soil health are addressed simultaneously.

Fig.4: LH1 forestry activities¹

Rotational Grazing is one of the most widespread and transformative interventions across the Dehesa. Rotational grazing is a system in which livestock, primarily sheep and cattle, are systematically moved across different parcels of land, mimicking natural herd movement. By allowing animals to graze only a small portion of the land at a time, this method prevents overgrazing and gives previously grazed areas ample time to rest, regenerate, and support the regrowth of grasses and the restoration of the soil ecosystem. In some cases, farmers apply intensive grazing by concentrating animals in small areas for short periods, sometimes as little as one night per plot, before moving them to fresh ground. The impact of animal hooves is intentionally brief and intense, creating light soil disturbance that stimulates biological activity and nutrient cycling. The small indentations created by grazing enhance water infiltration and retention, which is crucial in the Dehesa's dry and heat-prone environment. The result is improved

¹ This Image is AI-generated

pasture resilience, increased plant diversity, and enhanced soil structure. After grazing, the area is left undisturbed for extended periods, often months or even years, to allow full ecological recovery. Simple equipment, including temporary fencing, using some posts and a wire, is used to manage grazing.

In holistic management, farmers commonly estimate animal days per hectare as a way to plan grazing. This is typically done through visual assessment, where they evaluate the area an animal requires to meet its daily nutritional needs. Based on this estimation, they calculate the available forage on a given plot and determine how many animal days that area can sustainably support.

Grass Finishing is another important technique used by several farmers. Instead of relying on external feed inputs, animals are fattened entirely on pasture. This not only reduces dependence on industrial feed but also produces high-quality meat with a lower environmental footprint. Farmers may include small amounts of supplements during the drier summer months, when pasture quality and nutritional value naturally decline.

These interventions are deeply rooted in **holistic management**, a decision-making framework that integrates ecological, economic, and social dimensions into land-use planning. Unlike conventional forestry or agricultural approaches, holistic management emphasizes adaptive, systems-based thinking. Farmers use planning tools to design rotational grazing schedules, monitor pasture conditions, and adjust their management based on seasonal changes and ecological feedback. A key component of this approach is understanding the relationship between soil health, productivity, and grazing. Farmers conduct soil tests and field observations to assess the impact of grazing, determine appropriate rest periods, and tailor practices to the specific needs of their land. The type of livestock, soil composition, and ecological response all influence outcomes; each plot reacts differently and therefore requires site-specific research and adaptive management to align grazing practices with the provision of ecosystem services. This approach encourages long-term thinking and reinforces the connection between agroforestry practices and ecosystem health, enhancing both soil regeneration and animal well-being.

4.2. Drivers and barriers to implement soil health practices in Lighthouse 1

While the adoption of these holistic management and regenerative grazing practices has shown to offer clear ecological and economic benefits, there are still a range of barriers farmers might face to implement these practices. Insights from the interviews highlight both the motivations behind adoption and the practical challenges that slow wider uptake. Table 5 provides an overview of the drivers and barriers to implementing and scaling soil health practices in LH6.

For more details, a more comprehensive synthesis of the barriers and drivers for LH1 is provided in Annex 8.4.1.

Table 5: Drivers and barriers to implementing soil health practices in LH1

Category	Sub-Category	Drivers	Barriers
Environment	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversity)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Natural Regeneration of native plants observed quickly - Improved biodiversity and animal fertility through rotational grazing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Resting parts of land may be seen as “lost” productive area due to rotational grazing - Grass finishing difficult to achieve in the Mediterranean climate - Long resting periods are needed to enable the establishment of perennial grasses
	<i>Soil health</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rapid improvement in soil health and vegetation from rotational grazing - Enhanced soil structure and water retention increase landscape-level resilience to land degradation and drought 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Rotational grazing Requires regular planning and adaptive monitoring, which can be seen as labour intensive. - Soil benefits depend on consistency and commitment over time.
	<i>Carbon Sequestration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility of entering the carbon market by monitoring carbon sequestration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Need years of data in order to enter the carbon market - Need resources and time to monitor
Economic	<i>Agronomic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial setup of rotational grazing systems is relatively inexpensive - Reduced input costs—mainly feed, and water where irrigation (rarely) applies - Holistic management helps reverse land degradation and improves long term productivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Short term perceived productivity loss when land is rested - Labour intensive management practices
Social	<i>Society & community</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer learning and regenerative farming networks help share practices and results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited number of formal training or demonstration sites - Lack of widespread exposure to success stories
	<i>Workforce</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers adopting these practices often come from non-agricultural backgrounds and are more open to innovation and systems thinking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Older / traditionally trained farmers may resist to change - Labour requirements for rotational grazing (frequent livestock movement)
Institutional	<i>Public policy</i>	/	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of high-level institutional support for holistic management

4.3. Ex-post agroforestry impact assessment

To assess the impact of LH1's agroforestry and soil health practices, the ex-post forestry assessment tool (Figure 2) was filled in for LH1. This resulted in **ex-post agroforestry assessment tool**, visualized in Figure 5. Because farmers reported only positive outcomes from the regenerative practices implemented at LH1, this assessment tool focuses exclusively on those impacts. No direct negative effects were identified in relation to holistic management techniques such as rotational grazing and grass finishing.

Rooted in the local context of silvopastoral land use, the tool captures observed outcomes shared by farmers, practitioners, and local networks following the application of regenerative and holistic management approaches. It offers a structured overview of social, economic, environmental, and institutional impacts, reflecting how farmer-led innovation contributes to soil restoration, biodiversity, and rural vitality. This tool supports evidence-based learning, facilitates knowledge exchange and highlights scalable strategies for improving soil health.

For a more complete synthesis of the impacts of LH1, please refer to Annex 8.5.1

Fig.5: Ex-post agroforestry impact assessment tool LH1

4.4. Relation to soil health indicators for lighthouse 1

The environmental impacts observed in LH1 can be further associated with key soil health indicators (see Table 6), which help frame these outcomes within recognized soil functions. Improvements in soil structure and water retention reported by farmers are consistent with structural indicators such as bulk density and soil water dynamics. Increased vegetation cover and landscape regeneration align with vegetation-based indicators such as NDVI and ground cover, reflecting enhanced productivity and resilience under dry conditions. Observed gains in biodiversity are linked to biological indicators, including microbial activity and diversity, while the role of regenerative practices in supporting carbon sequestration relates to soil organic carbon. Although not quantitatively assessed in this study, these indicators provide a structured lens to interpret the observed environmental impacts associated with holistic land management in LH1. This alignment between stakeholder-observed impacts and the soil health indicators developed in WP3 strengthens the consistency between qualitative field insights and the project's assessment of soil ecosystem services.

Table 6: Linking observed impacts to soil health indicators for LH6

Practice implemented	Observed impact	Related soil function	Linked soil health indicators
Rotational Grazing	Improved soil structure through grazing (hoof action, porosity)	Soil structure	Bulk density
Rotational Grazing	Increased water infiltration and retention	Water regulation	Bulk density & water content at field capacity
Rotational Grazing	Increased vegetation cover and pasture regeneration	Erosion control	Vegetation cover
Rotational Grazing & grass finishing	Increased soil biodiversity and biological activity	Soil biodiversity	Total PLFAs, Fungal Chao1 Index & Fungal Shannon Index
Rotational Grazing	Improved carbon sequestration potential	Climate regulation	Total organic carbon

5. Lighthouse 6: Latvian forest

LH6 is the Forest research station in the Mežole region of Latvia, an experimental site representing Boreal forest soil. Spanning over 9 959 hectares, the forest is situated in the region of Vidzeme in northeast Latvia. The site is coordinated by the Latvian State Forest Research Institute (SILAVA) with Forest research station technical support. The Vidzeme region is characterised by natural landscapes, including forests (56%) and agricultural land (34%). The main tree species are Scots pine (19.8%), Norway spruce (46.8%), birch (22.7%), black alder (5.7%) and aspen (3.9%). The average annual precipitation in Latvia is 667 mm. The months with most precipitation are July and August, in each of which average rainfall is 78 mm. The least precipitation is in February and March – each of which has on average 33 mm.

The primary challenge at LH6 is nutrient depletion, driven by soil acidification and nutrient leaching or immobilization in spruce forest stands. This issue is further exacerbated by whole-tree biomass harvesting, which involves removing not only the trunk but also the tops and branches. In addition, the area's sloping terrain combined with rainfall contributes to soil erosion, the displacement of organic matter, and increased soil acidification. Figure 6 further provides some pictures taken during the field visit of LH6 when interviewing stakeholders. Table 7, showcases an overview of LH6.

Table 7: LH6 overview (from D2.2)

LH Coordinator partner	Latvian State Forest Research Institute "Silava", The Forest Research Station
LH name (location)	Mežole
Region	Vidzeme
Country	Latvia
Area (Ha)	9 959.5 ha
Soil health challenges	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diverse soil organic matter content • Unbalanced soil nutrient content • Soil acidification • Soil erosion on slopes • Former sand/gravel mining areas in different recultivation stages

Fig.8: LH6 landscape

The context of LH6 is further reflected through key soil health indicators identified in WP3 that characterize this boreal forest system. Indicators such as pH and cation exchange capacity highlight ongoing challenges related to soil acidification and nutrient balance, while total organic carbon reflects the role of these soils in carbon sequestration and storage and climate regulation. Structural sensitivity to forest operations is captured through bulk density, indicating potential risks of compaction. At the same time, biological indicators point to the importance of maintaining soil biodiversity for ecosystem functioning. In addition, land surface temperature (LST) reflects broader environmental conditions influencing soil moisture and vegetation dynamics. Together, these indicators frame LH6 as a managed forest system where soil stability, nutrient dynamics, and biological activity are key to sustaining long-term productivity and resilience. Table 8 provides an overview of the main soil health indicators assessed in WP3 for LH6. While this study does not present quantitative values, these indicators offer important context for understanding the soil conditions of LH6

Table 8: Most sensitive soil health indicators for LH6

Category ES	Soil Ecosystem Services	Soil health indicators
Provisioning	Provision of fibre, energy or raw materials	Timber production
Regulating	Nutrient cycling	PH, Available phosphorus & Cation exchange capacity
	Flood regulation and water storage	Bulk density & Drought Stress Index (DSI)
	Climate regulation	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST), Total organic carbon, Particulate soil organic carbon & Soil moisture
Supporting	Biodiversity	Prokaryotic Chao1 Index & Prokaryotic Shannon Index
		Zygomycota abundance
		Total PLFAs

5.1. Description and interventions of Lighthouse 6

The Mežole region forest is subject to formal forest management restrictions for nature conservation, underscoring its ecological value and the careful balance required between commercial activity and environmental conservation.

Latvia's forest landscape is divided evenly between public and private ownership. Half of the forests are state-owned and managed by the state enterprise JSC Latvian State Forests (LVM), which is tasked with ensuring the long-term ecological and economic sustainability of the country's forest resources. The remaining 50% is privately held, predominantly by individuals or small companies.

SILAVA, the coordinator of LH6, is Latvia's leading forestry research institute. It designs and tests sustainable forestry practices, combining ecological monitoring with applied innovation. Within the Mežole region forest, SILAVA conducts long-term experiments on soil health, reforestation, biodiversity, and forest operations - including fertilization - generating data and guidelines that inform national forest management.

To better understand how LH6 operates within the broader Latvian forest management system, a series of structured interviews was conducted with public officials, research scientists and private forest managers. Their insights reveal the interplay between scientific research, regulatory environments, economic drivers, and conservation goals in shaping soil and forest management practices. Table 9 provides an overview of the interviewed stakeholders, highlighting their roles, institutional affiliations, and specific connections to LH6.

Table 9: Stakeholders interviewed for LH6

LH6 stakeholders interviewed		
Name	Organisation	Role description
Raivo Ošis	SILAVA/Stora Enso Latvia	Former forest manager and researcher/ Harvesting manager
Zane Libiete	SILAVA	Senior researcher, Forester and on-site researcher
Jordane Jean-Claude Champion	SILAVA	Forestry engineer on forest management and practices
Baiba Jansone	Latvian University of Life Sciences and Technologies	Associated Professor specialized in forestry
Edmunds Linde	Latvian State Forests	Director of managing state forest lands according to social, environmental and economic purposes

5.1.1. Lighthouse 6 business model

Table 10 presents the business model for LH6. This model reflects a synthesis of forestry-related research, business operations, and public engagement across Latvian forest systems. Unlike LH1, which is shaped by farmer-led experimentation, LH6 integrates a broader, institutionally driven research and forestry management approach applied across both state and private owned forests.

The Mežole serves as a research-intensive landscape within this context, combining rigorous experimentation on soil health, biodiversity and forest regeneration. The model serves as a **sustainable business model framework for research-driven forestry** supporting resilient ecosystem services. It is an adaptive tool that can inspire similar forest management approaches at other sites.

While the forestry practices and their impacts will be examined in more detail in the following sections, this model already offers a clear illustration of how research-driven approaches are practically implemented across both public and private forest landscapes.

Key value proposition

The LH6 value proposition lies in integrating scientific research with practical forest management to foster sustainable forestry across Latvia. Key outputs include timber, reforestation services, ecosystem conservation, public access, and policy-relevant research. The region's landscape-level interventions are designed to maintain long-term productivity while promoting soil health, biodiversity, and social values.

Key partnerships

SILAVA, Latvian State Forest Research Institute, coordinates studies, manages research plots, and develops technologies to support sustainable forest management - both at the Forest Research Station and as a source of expertise for the broader forestry industry. SILAVA collaborates closely with the state-owned Latvian State Forests (LVM), which manages 50% of the country's forests. While no peer-led network seems to exist in LH6, collaboration with policymakers, NGOs, and research bodies ensures a broad, multi-level support structure for soil health practices and forestry innovation.

Key beneficiaries / customers

For state-owned forests, the primary customers are timber buyers and public users accessing the forest for recreation. For research forests, beneficiaries include academic institutions and EU-funded initiatives. Moreover, the public benefits through free access to forests for hiking, berry picking, and forestry education. Meanwhile, businesses and private forest owners derive profit from timber, hunting, and leasing land for extraction activities.

Governance

Half of the forest land is managed by the state through LVM under strict regulatory frameworks, while the other half is privately owned. Research institutions also play a role in governance as they use public-owned land for research purposes. Forest

governance is further influenced by EU policy, national certification schemes, and NGO advocacy, which is strongly present in Latvia.

Key resources & services

The model relies heavily on institutional knowledge, research infrastructure, and access to state-managed land. Key assets - such as laboratories, field stations, specialized forestry equipment, and advanced technologies like drones for remote monitoring - are central to effective forest management in Latvia. Core services encompass seed and sapling production, data collection, recreational area management, and comprehensive environmental monitoring.

Cost structure & revenue streams

Main costs are due to advanced data systems, and the labour-intensive nature of forest maintenance, while revenues come from timber sales, hunting leases, seedling production, and European and public funded projects. These include national research grants from the Latvian Council of Science, the State Research Programme *Forest4LV* on new forest services and soil studies, and other targeted projects on fungi, forest resilience, and upcoming agrivoltaics. Public access and educational offerings provide social return on investment, while carbon markets remain an emerging (yet unrealized) revenue potential.

Table 10: Research-driven forestry business model framework for LH6

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value propositions	Key beneficiaries / Customers	Governance
SILAVA – Research and development Latvian State Forest (LVM) – Management of state forests EU-funded projects Private forest owners Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies Ministry of Agriculture	Forest management <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Harvesting Planting & replanting Soil preparation Afforestation Forest monitoring Use of remote sensing, GIS tools and drones Soil and Environmental Monitoring - Soil sampling & analysis Research and Innovation - Development of new forestry practices Public recreation services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Trail development Christmas tree harvesting Educational programs – demonstration plots for projects & forestry professionals Policy Influence and Standards Development – Engagement with NGO's and LVM	Sustainable timber production Public access and cultural services <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Berry & mushroom picking Hiking, biking, nature appreciation Seasonal and cultural activities (e.g. Christmas tree cutting) Educational programs - On-site learning for schools & universities Scientific research and innovation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generation of knowledge on forest regeneration, soil health, and biodiversity Field testing of new management techniques and soil health practices Forest ecosystem services and biodiversity conservation Soil and water conservation within forestry landscapes Policy Support	Commercial and industry actors - Timber buyers and processors Research, education, and innovation stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Researchers and academics with access to pilot sites University students and forestry trainees Forest visitors and local communities Governance and policy actors	State-led governance through LVM Private ownership Research governance influence NGO influence
	Key resources		Key Services	
	Institutional and human capital <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scientific and technical staff Knowledge base Physical and technological infrastructure <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Forestry machinery Monitoring and sampling tools Experimental forest plots Drone technology 		Forest Regeneration – replanting, forest thinning, maintenance, fertilization Environmental Research & ecological forestry studies Educational & knowledge exchange Public recreation and access	
	Cost structure		Revenue streams	
	Operational - Machinery & monitoring equipment Human resource – labour &, scientific staffing Research – monitoring, analysis & lab testing		Timber sales Seed and sapling production Public services – hunting leases Research grants – EU projects, state-funded projects, industry directly funded research	

5.1.2. Lighthouse 6 forestry interventions related to soil health

Forestry interventions in LH6, reflect a dual purpose: sustaining timber production while enhancing long-term ecological resilience, especially in relation to soil health. Although the active implementation of specific soil health practices in LH6 is still emerging—partly due to its primary focus on timber production—the landscape functions as a research-driven environment dedicated to advancing the integration of sustainable practices within commercial forestry operations, sustainable forest management, advanced monitoring technologies, and public engagement.

Fig.7: LH6 forestry activities²

Forest regeneration and afforestation

At the core of LH6 are foundational silvicultural practices that ensure the regeneration and productivity of forest stands. These include harvesting operations, planting and replanting, and soil preparation techniques designed to promote optimal tree establishment and reduce erosion on slopes. Afforestation initiatives are also undertaken in previously degraded or non-forested areas, supporting land restoration objectives. These forest interventions are conducted under strict sustainability mandates, particularly in state-owned forests managed by LVM and at the Forest Research Station. These areas follow certification standards that require not only replanting but also attention to site-specific ecological impacts.

Timber production

² This image is AI-generated

Timber production remains a core economic function in both public and privately owned Latvian forests, and it plays a major role in shaping forest management interventions.

Soil and environmental monitoring

A defining feature of LH6 is its research-based approach to soil health. SILAVA conducts regular soil sampling and analysis, examining variables such as pH, organic matter content, nutrient balances, and signs of acidification or erosion. These assessments inform adaptive interventions and contribute to the national body of knowledge on how forest practices influence soil ecosystems over time.

Advanced environmental monitoring tools are also employed, including remote sensing technologies, GIS-based forest mapping, and in some cases, drone-assisted monitoring. These tools help assess canopy health, biomass recovery, and areas vulnerable to degradation, enabling precise spatial planning.

Research and innovation

LH6 serves as a living laboratory for forestry innovation. SILAVA continuously develops and tests new forestry practices, including low-impact harvesting methods, alternative regeneration strategies, and soil conservation techniques. Many of these practices are first validated in experimental plots before being recommended for broader national adoption.

Public recreation and cultural engagement

Forests in Latvia are not just economic or ecological assets but also provide cultural landscapes. The forests include trails for hiking and biking. These trails give people easy access to the forest, supporting traditional activities such as berry and mushroom picking across all types of forest ownership, and Christmas tree harvesting specifically in the state-owned forests managed by JSC Latvian State Forests. These services require careful planning to minimize the ecological impact of trails and human activity, particularly along forest edges and high-traffic zones. Their deliberate integration into forest management reflects a commitment to multifunctional land use, balancing ecological integrity, cultural value, and public access.

Educational and demonstration activities

Demonstration plots are used to share best practices with forestry professionals, and students. These plots showcase real-time results of forest interventions, such as species-specific growth responses, soil treatment effects, and regeneration outcomes. The plots serve as vital tools for capacity building within both state agencies and private landowner networks.

Policy influence and standards development

Finally, these forests play a strategic role in shaping forest governance through policy engagement and standard-setting. By working closely with the Latvian State Forests (LVM), NGOs, and government agencies, SILAVA ensures that field-level insights could translate into policy. State-owned forests managed by Forest Research Station, in particular, serve as exemplars for sustainable practice, allowing LH6 to bridge the gap between scientific knowledge and regulatory forest management.

5.2. Drivers and barriers to implement soil health practices in Lighthouse 6

Table 11 provides an overview of the drivers and barriers connected to LH6 in the implementation and scaling of soil health practices across forest landscapes. For a more detailed synthesis of drivers and barriers please refer to Annex 8.4.2.

Table 11: Drivers and barriers to implementing soil health practices in LH6

Category	Sub-Category	Drivers	Barriers
Environment	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversity)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Biodiversity depletion due to lack of nutrients or eutrophication - Afforestation and tree protection - Enhance habitat quality for crops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restriction to forest management activities in protected areas
	<i>Soil health</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The need to address soil health challenges to sustain long-term forestry productivity (Unbalanced soil nutrient content, Soil acidification & Soil erosion on slopes). - SHP improve erosion control, water retention, and nutrient stability, which in turn support healthier and faster-growing trees. - Drones in plots enable early, precise detection of localized damage, which helps reduce overall impact and improve the strategic use of SHP. - SHP support forest resilience and yield. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long term benefits vs short-term productivity losses. - Technical complexity due to variability in soil types and conditions.
	<i>Carbon Sequestration</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - SHP support soil organic matter retention and reduce degradation, indirectly contributing to carbon sequestration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Natural processes in soil causing organic matter decomposition - Weather extremes, spread of diseases and insects
Economic	<i>Agronomic</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improved site sustainability and timber yield from SHP. - Research trials, like SILAVA, generate data to optimize long-term productivity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High expenses linked to soil analysis and equipment. - Private forest owners frequently lack the economic margin to invest in practices that don't yield immediate returns. - Limited and short research funding cycles constrain the ability to demonstrate long-term soil impacts. - Lack of commercial incentives of timber market to prioritise soil health (specifically for small scale foresters).
Social	<i>Society & community</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Public land must respond to scrutiny from NGOs and civil society. - Social pressure to meet sustainability expectations in sensitive ecosystems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forest owners/ managers often lack access to site-specific SHP recommendations or training. - Lack of awareness
	<i>Workforce</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - New more ergonomic machines and more comfortable and light equipment come to the market and practice. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Forestry work remains physically demanding. - Latvia is experiencing a decline in new generation workforce. - Staffing limitations hinder consistent field monitoring and adaptive intervention.
Institutional	<i>Public policy</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - State forest mandates require environmental stewardship & compliance with certification standards (e.g. PEFC). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research forests depend on short term grants that limit scalability. - Lack of national regulations - Lack of clear, accessible technical guidelines for SHP.

5.3. Ex-post forestry impact assessment

To assess the impact of LH6's forestry and soil health practices, the **ex-post forestry assessment tool** (Figure 2) was filled in for LH6, see Figure 8. This tool captures the outcomes observed and reported by farmers, researchers, and local stakeholders following the implementation of both conventional forestry practices - such as timber production and forest management - and more sustainable interventions, including afforestation efforts and research focused on soil health. It provides a structured overview of social, economic, environmental, and institutional impacts, helping to contextualize local experiences while offering broader insights. The tool presents key insights from interviewed stakeholders and supports evidence-based decision-making. It aims to inspire foresters, researchers, and land managers to adopt practices that enhance soil structure and strengthen overall ecosystem resilience.

For a more complete synthesis of the impacts of LH6, please refer to Annex 8.5.2

Fig.8: Ex-post forestry impact assessment tool LH6

5.4. Relation to soil health indicators for lighthouse 6

The environmental impacts observed in LH6 can be linked to the key soil health indicators under WP3 (see Table 12), which help frame these outcomes within recognised soil functions. Reported challenges, such as soil compaction and disturbance from forestry operations, are consistent with structural indicators such as bulk density. The role of forest systems in carbon sequestration is captured through indicators such as soil organic carbon, while biological indicators show the importance of maintaining soil biodiversity for ecosystem functioning. In addition, broader environmental conditions influencing soil moisture and vegetation dynamics can be linked to indicators such as land surface temperature. Although not quantitatively assessed in this study, these indicators provide a structured lens to interpret the environmental observed impacts and trade-offs associated with forest management practices in LH6. This alignment between stakeholder-observed impacts and the soil health indicators developed in WP3 strengthens the consistency between qualitative field insights and the project's assessment of soil ecosystem services.

Table 12: Linking observed impacts to soil health indicators for LH6

Practice implemented	Observed impact	Related soil function	Linked soil health indicators
Timber production (harvesting and machinery use)	Soil compaction from machinery	Soil structure	Bulk density & soil moisture
Public recreation & timber production	Microplastics infiltrate soils & water systems	Soil biodiversity	Total PLFAs, Prokaryotic Chao1 Index & Prokaryotic Shannon Index
Forest regeneration & afforestation	Soil acidification	Nutrient cycling	PH & Cation exchange capacity
Soil monitoring & forestry research & timber production	Carbon sequestration role of forests	Climate regulation	Albedo and Land surface temperature (LST) & Total organic carbon
Forest regeneration & afforestation	Biodiversity importance in forest soils	Soil biodiversity	Total PLFAs, Zygomycota abundance, Prokaryotic Chao1 Index
Forest regeneration & afforestation	Water retention / erosion dynamics	Water regulation	Bulk density & Drought Stress Index (DSI)

6. Discussion

6.1. Comparative analysis and key takeaways

In both LH1 and LH6, the emphasis on soil health represents a central component of their sustainability agendas, though the approach and degree of implementation differ significantly. Table 13 provides a comparative overview of LH1 and LH6 on some key dimensions.

Table 13: Comparative analysis LH1 & LH6

	Category	LH1: La Dehesa	LH6: Mežole
Land context	Landscape type	Agroforest & silvopastoral system	Boreal forest
	Main land use	Regenerative livestock farming	Timber production & forestry research
Business model dimensions	Governance	Family-managed farms with local networks	State-managed and private ownership with research coordination
	Partnerships	Local farmer networks	Research and state bodies collaboration
	Forestry practices	Rotational grazing & Holistic management	Harvesting, Planting & Afforestation
	Soil health focus	Farmer-led observation and adaptive grazing	Research-informed with precision tools
	Main Produce	Meat, dairy and wool produce	Timber production
Impact dimensions	Societal	Local network & peer-to-peer learning	Forest recreation activities & cultural forest traditions
	Economic	Product diversification & local markets	Timber revenue, seedling production & research grants
	Environmental	Soil fertility, drought resilience, carbon sequestration & biodiversity	Erosion control & biodiversity
	Institutional / legal	Strengthen farmer networks and cooperatives	Policy for forestry standard

In LH1, soil practices are deeply embedded in agroecological livestock systems, where farmers use rotational grazing and adaptive land management to enhance soil structure, water retention, and fertility. In contrast, LH6 integrates soil health into a forestry-focused research landscape, using monitoring technologies (drones, GIS) and afforestation to address issues like erosion, acidification, and nutrient loss.

What unites both landscapes is a clear emphasis on site-specific, ecosystem-based approaches, each responding to its own biophysical and economic context. LH1 demonstrates how farmer-led networks and experiential learning can drive soil restoration, while LH6 shows the value of institutional coordination and technological monitoring in aligning forest productivity with environmental care. Following the comparative analysis, some key takeaways are highlighted below. We present a simplified business model, see Table 14, that highlights the key elements to consider when implementing soil health practices within sustainable forest management.

Collaborative knowledge systems

A key takeaway for other European forests is the importance of collaboration between stakeholders. Whether through farmer networks, formal research institutions, or cooperative bodies, it is the strength of knowledge exchange and local engagement that enables soil health innovations to take root. Other forests can learn from LH1's model of peer-to-peer diffusion and LH6's example of integrating science and practice to guide scalable, context-adapted solutions. Linking different forms of knowledge, scientific, traditional and experiential, can enrich the innovation system in place.

Diverse landscape functions

LH1 and LH6 show that soil health can be addressed through very different operational systems, agroforestry (LH1) and timber-oriented forestry (LH6). This suggests there is no one-size-fits-all approach. What matters is integrating soil considerations into core land use objectives, whether those involve grazing, harvesting, or conservation. By integrating sustainable practices, these sites develop a diverse value proposition that includes production, training, recreational and cultural activities, and enhanced environmental resilience.

Feedback loops

Both LHs use feedback loops: LH1 via observational grazing responses, LH6 through remote sensing and sampling. These loops are what allow land managers to adapt and improve over time. Effective soil health strategies rely on feedback systems, whether low-tech or high-tech, to support learning and adaptive decision-making. Although achieving this balance takes time, it is crucial to adopt land management approaches that support both economic viability and optimal ecological performance.

Diverse revenue models

LH1 and LH6 show how different landscapes draw on distinct revenue streams to support sustainable land and soil management. LH1 farmers diversify income through product sales (meat, wool, olive oil), training services, and potential access to carbon markets. LH6, by contrast, relies on timber production, seedling sales,

hunting leases, and research grants. Together, they highlight the importance of context-specific revenue models, combining commercial outputs, public funding, and ecosystem service opportunities, to make soil health financially viable across diverse forest systems in Europe.

Table 14: Sustainable forestry business model – key takeaways

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value propositions	Key beneficiaries / Customers	Governance
Collaborative knowledge systems – knowledge sharing between stakeholder groups including farmer networks, formal research institutions, or cooperative bodied and public institutions	Feedback loops – continuously monitor and understand the interaction between implemented soil health practices and observed impacts Diverse landscape functions – Integrate contextual soil considerations into core land use objectives	Deliver multifunctional benefits – soil health, biodiversity, commercial value, knowledge-sharing	Diverse customer base - from commercial buyers (timber, meat, olive oil, wool) to public and academic institutions engaged in research & education and local residents	Multi-level collaboration - strong links between practitioners, research bodies, and public authorities
	Key resources		Key Services	
	Build peer networks and knowledge systems		Multifunctional services for communities & environments - offer ecosystem services, education, recreation, and climate-related benefits	
Cost & Revenue structure				
Diverse revenue models - Different landscapes draw on distinct revenue streams to support sustainable land and soil management				

6.2. Carbon credits

Farmers interviewed from La Dehesa have begun exploring the carbon credit market to expand their revenue streams. Their interest in carbon credits reflects a broader commitment to integrating ecological objectives into a financially viable business model. By linking soil health improvements and rotational grazing practices with measurable climate benefits, these farmers aim to unlock financial incentives that reinforce their sustainable approach. Given this section explores carbon credits, we provide a quick overview of typical steps farmers / foresters should take in order to earn credits.

1. **Establish baseline and estimate potential:** A project developer or agronomist helps assess existing carbon stocks to estimate how many credits might be earned (based on farm size, soil, current practices).
2. **Adopt carbon-friendly practices:** Farmers implement additional farm or forestry practices that boost carbon sequestration. These practices cannot be changed during the carbon measuring period (typical 5 years).
3. **Monitor and measure:** After each year of implementing the new practice, data is collected on soil carbon or biomass changes. This may involve soil sampling, remote sensing or other data. Some projects use models to estimate annual sequestration.
4. **Third-party verification:** An independent verifier reviews the data and confirms the carbon gains. They ensure the results are real, additional (beyond business-as-usual), and permanent.
5. **Issue and sell credits:** Once verified, carbon credits are issued (registered) on a recognized registry. Farmers then sell the credits either directly to buyers, through intermediaries, or on carbon exchanges receiving payment (for example, per tonne of CO₂ sequestered).

Figure 9 provides an overview of the carbon credit market mechanism (Lelechenko, 2024).

Fig.9: Carbon credit market mechanism

Farmers in LH1 have begun engaging with the carbon credit market by exploring the necessary steps for entry, including collaboration with organizations to establish carbon sequestration baselines and implement ongoing monitoring. These initiatives reflect the broader mindset of the farmers interviewed - representative of a new generation - who are actively seeking to implement more innovative and sustainable practices. However, they also emphasized that the carbon credit market remains difficult to access, characterized by technical complexity, evolving standards, and limited accessibility for independent land managers.

In contrast, stakeholders interviewed for LH6 reported no current involvement in the carbon credit market. Notably, LVM, the state-owned organization responsible for managing a large portion of Latvia's forests, has not yet initiated any steps toward participating in carbon credit mechanisms.

The contrasting levels of engagement between LH1 and LH6 highlight the need to better understand both the challenges and opportunities associated with carbon credit schemes. This section explores the structural barriers faced by farmers and foresters, as well as the potential for carbon markets to support sustainable land management when effectively implemented.

6.2.1. Carbon credit market analysis to LH1

LH1's business model provides both environmental and economic value through regenerative practices such as rotational grazing and silvopastoral systems. These interventions naturally enhance soil organic carbon, improve water retention, and support the recovery of degraded land. As a result, previously dry and degraded landscapes are being transformed into greener, more productive agroforestry systems with diverse vegetation and tree cover. Farmers have already reported reduced operational costs and increased revenue, particularly from the sale of premium-quality products. Participation in carbon credit markets presents an additional opportunity to diversify income streams, enabling farmers to monetise their soil improvements while aligning economic returns with measurable environmental benefits. We present an overview of key opportunities and challenges identified by the interviewed farmers in La Dehesa regarding participation in soil carbon credit markets. These insights reflect both the practical potential and systemic limitations tied to the carbon credit market.

These findings for LH1 emerged through the interviews conducted and an additional in-person workshop conducted in La Dehesa with InBestSoil project partners, including WU, University of Exeter, LGI, Zabala, Actyva, and Fundación Global Nature. The workshop, conducted under Work Package 5, Task 5.2: *"Exploring the potential of socio-ecological and technological innovation pathways to support the development of business strategies and cases for soil health,"* focused on payment schemes for ecosystem services, with dedicated discussions on both the potential and challenges of carbon credit mechanisms.

Opportunities:

- **Environmental restoration potential:** The La Dehesa landscape, marked by frequent droughts and high temperatures, presents a high potential for

ecological regeneration. Its degraded conditions provide a strong baseline for improvement through regenerative practices, enabling significant gains in soil carbon sequestration, water retention, and overall ecosystem resilience.

- **Income diversification:** Participation in carbon markets allows farmers to complement their traditional revenue streams (e.g., meat, wool, olive oil) with payments for ecosystem services, making their operations more financially resilient.
- **Valuation of ecosystem services:** Carbon credits offer farmers to receive financial compensation for restoring soil health, enhancing biodiversity, and increasing carbon storage in La Dehesa. This could provide further incentive for other farmers in the region to recognize the value of restored ecosystem services.
- **Peer learning and networks:** Emerging farmer-led networks are fostering shared learning around carbon schemes by exchanging experiences, building peer support, and connecting fellow farmers to practical resources and organizations that offer guidance on carbon monitoring and certification.
- **Access through EU project involvement:** Participation in EU-funded initiatives has expanded La Dehesa farmers' access to carbon credit mechanisms and key stakeholders. These projects could help connect farmers with specialized organizations that support engagement in carbon monitoring, certification processes, and linking with potential buyers.
- **Increasing corporate pressure:** Rising pressure on corporations to reduce emissions is increasing demand for carbon credits. This trend presents an opportunity for La Dehesa farmers to market carbon credits as verified contributions to global climate targets.
- **Pioneering role for farmers:** The interviewed farmers in La Dehesa have shown a strong commitment to innovation, moving away from conventional practices rooted in generational tradition. Carbon markets offer these farmers a chance to pioneer in a new, evolving space that rewards sustainable land management.

Challenges:

- **Long-term contracts and data demands:** Carbon credit schemes often require long-term commitments (typically 5+ years), including ongoing data collection and third-party verification. During this period, farmers are restricted from changing practices, which can limit adaptive land management in response to external pressures.
- **Cost and technical barriers:** Measuring soil carbon accurately can be costly and technologically demanding. Small-scale farmers in La Dehesa may lack access to suitable partners, tools, or technical know-how to participate effectively in carbon markets.
- **Equity concerns:** Farmers who have already implemented regenerative practices may have less opportunity to generate credits, as carbon gains are calculated based on improvement from an initial baseline. This disadvantages farmers, such as the interviewed farmers in la Dehesa, who

were early innovators in sustainable land management and started with a higher carbon baseline.

- **Low regional awareness:** Traditional farmers in La Dehesa often lack awareness of carbon credit opportunities. Interviewed farmers noted that more outreach and education are needed to expand participation and improve the system through collective experience.
- **Greenwashing risks:** Farmers expressed concerns about the potential misuse of credits by corporations, fearing that their efforts might be used to mask continued emissions elsewhere without achieving real climate benefits. Strong governance and transparency are essential to maintaining credibility.
- **Variability in environmental and geographical conditions:** Variability in soil types and climate across Spain makes it difficult to standardize carbon measurement. For instance, La Dehesa's dry, rocky soils will inherently sequester less carbon than wetter regions in the north. A one-size-fits-all approach risks unfairly undervaluing carbon efforts in drier areas. Farmers expressed their wish for tailored baselines and regional benchmarks for a fair and equitable credit system.

6.2.2. Carbon credit market analysis to LH6

Currently, LH6 is not involved in the carbon credit market. Overall, the development of the carbon credit market in the Baltic States, including Latvia, is still in its early stages. There are various challenges to the adoption and development of the carbon market, as well as landowner involvement to this market.

Challenges:

- **Insufficient information:** the lack of accessible, transparent, and reliable information about how the carbon market works and what benefits it can bring leads to low awareness and limited trust in the potential for profit.
- **Lack of successful examples:** there are few visible success stories of projects that have been implemented, monitored, and verified to generate income, which undermines confidence in the market.
- **Absence of clear regulations at both EU and national levels:** regulatory ambiguity creates uncertainty for investors, companies, and landowners, making long-term planning difficult.
- **Limited capacity and expertise:** Even when interest exists, there are too few specialized companies, consultants, and experts in many regions with the technical knowledge to design, implement, and manage carbon market projects.
- **Complexity and time-consuming processes:** Carbon market participation requires navigating complex steps such as certification, monitoring, reporting, and verification. These processes are not only technically demanding but also expensive and time-intensive.

At present, there is only one approved project on platforms maintained by private operators (a Verra afforestation project). There are no projects related to forest management, nor is there significant interest of landowners and managers, as the current price of carbon credits is not motivating enough to influence economic activity. Moreover, opportunities to obtain credits from forest land are limited and are associated with high uncertainty (risk), which makes participation in the carbon credit market challenging or even impossible (except for afforestation projects). Despite the risks, uncertainties, and other limiting aspects, there are opportunities for the carbon credit market in Latvia, particularly in the afforestation of land with organic soils or low-fertility/productivity mineral soils not used for agricultural production, as well as in the adoption of practices that enhance carbon sequestration and storage in tree biomass and soil in forest land. In addition, mechanisms that expand the credit market from just carbon credits to, for example, also biodiversity credits would provide additional environmental, climate and sustainability benefits.

6.2.3. Vision for the future of the carbon credit market

As the interviewed farmers in la Dehesa are getting more interested and familiar with the carbon credit market, they are also highlighting the need for systems that are more equitable, flexible and reflective of the local context and their environmental efforts. A central tension in this vision lies in how credits are awarded: should farmers be rewarded based on results or on the practices they implement?

Practice-based vs. results-based rewards

Results-based payments focus on measurable carbon outcomes. While based on scientific numbers, they risk disadvantaging early adopters who already implemented sustainable practices and improved soil carbon levels prior to measuring their carbon baseline. These farmers often have fewer marginal gains to show and may miss out on credit eligibility despite having long committed to regeneration. Additionally, the verification of outcomes typically takes years, which the interviewed farmers believe discourages farmers who need more immediate financial certainty.

In contrast, these farmers also highlighted that **practice-based payments** would provide a more inclusive scheme. Rewarding efforts such as rotational grazing, agroforestry, or compost application offers a tangible incentive to adopt holistic land management. They believe this would lower entry barriers, encourage a proactive mindset, and provide a stepping stone toward longer-term ecological improvements. For many of these farmers, practice-based models, which could provide subsidies for farm management, align better with the reality of farming, where change is gradual and context-dependent.

Broadening the scope: biodiversity credits

Farmers in La Dehesa expressed growing interest in a broader valuation framework beyond carbon, noting that soil carbon alone is difficult to assess due to its high variability. They emphasized that the silvopastoral model commonly

practiced in the region, which integrates crops, grasslands, tree cover, and animal grazing, is greatly geared towards enhancing biodiversity. The Dehesa is one of the most extensive High Nature Value (HNV) systems in Europe. As such, they see potential for a future carbon market to evolve into a multi-service reward system, one that includes additional ecosystem services such as biodiversity conservation.

Moreover, several farmers noted that biodiversity monitoring requires easier more accessible data collection than measuring changes in soil carbon, making it a more accessible entry point for environmental compensation. This underscores the importance of designing payment schemes that are adapted to local land-use systems, ecological conditions, and the practical capacities of land managers.

The Savory Institute's Ecological Outcome Verification (EOV) protocol is a holistic land monitoring and verification framework designed to track the ecological outcomes of land management practices over time. It advocates for a carbon+ approach, meaning it goes beyond measuring carbon sequestration alone to also account for broader ecosystem health indicators—such as biodiversity, soil fertility, water retention, and ecosystem resilience. This comprehensive perspective acknowledges that sustainable land regeneration cannot be captured by carbon metrics alone, and instead requires an integrated view of ecological function (Savory Institute, 2025).

Adaptive and contextual payment schemes

Farmers also highlighted the needs for a system that is more dynamic and regionally sensitive. For example, incremental pricing mechanisms could reward higher sequestration rates with proportionally greater financial returns, while also factoring in regional climatic constraints and the cost of practices needed to achieve such outcomes. This helps ensure fair compensation across diverse landscapes, whether in humid northern forests or arid Mediterranean landscapes in Spain.

Putting Farmers at the center

To strengthen farmer's decision-making within the carbon market schemes, interviewed farmers expressed a clear desire to play a more central role in their design and operation. This means giving farmers a greater pricing autonomy, simplifying access to data and certification tools, and ensuring transparency in how credits are calculated and traded. By allowing farmers to set their own credit prices and decide how their credits are marketed or bundled, the system becomes more empowering.

In summary, the carbon credit market remains an emerging opportunity within the forestry sector, with varying levels of engagement across regions. For example, LH1 shows more active exploration of carbon schemes, while LH6 reflects a more research-oriented approach with limited direct involvement. These differences are shaped by local environmental conditions, land management practices, stakeholder interest and awareness in the market. Farmers who have expressed interest, particularly those interviewed for LH1, highlight the need for a more flexible and inclusive market structure. They advocate for payment schemes that

not only reward measurable carbon outcomes but also recognize the value of sustainable practices and broader ecosystem benefits, such as biodiversity enhancement. This reflects a call for multi-dimensional credit systems that better capture the full scope of farmers' environmental efforts.

7. Conclusion

This ex-post assessment underscores the diverse yet complementary pathways through which forestry systems can enhance soil health and ecological resilience. By examining LH1 and LH6 - two contrasting landscapes in terms of land use, governance, and intervention strategies - the study reveals that both farmer-led agroforestry and research-driven forest management can yield measurable environmental, social, and economic impacts when soil health is placed at the center of decision-making.

Key tools developed in this study, including a structured interview guide, tailored business model frameworks, and replicable impact assessment tools, equip stakeholders with practical frameworks to assess and improve forestry practices. The findings demonstrate that multi-actor collaboration, continuous monitoring, and adaptive management are central to sustainable outcomes.

The experience of LH1 highlights the role of peer-led innovation and regenerative farm practices in restoring Mediterranean silvopastoral systems, while LH6 illustrates how public-sector coordination and scientific experimentation can help shape boreal forest strategies for long-term resilience. Their combined lessons confirm that forest systems across Europe benefit from tailored solutions that reflect their specific environmental context and institutional realities.

Importantly, both cases show that improving soil health in forestry depends not only on technical knowledge, but also viable business models and supportive policies. Moving forward, the insights and tools provided in this report can inform broader efforts under the Mission Soil objectives and support the design of scalable, site-responsive forestry models that sustain both ecosystems and forest-based revenues.

8. Annex

8.1. Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide

PART 1: Introduction & background information

Organization description

<i>Organization Description</i>	<i>Response</i>
Name Organization	
Type Organization	
Mission & Activity Organization	

Profile description

<i>Profile Description</i>	<i>Response</i>
Name	
Role	
Activities	
Education / Forestry Experience	

Forestry characteristics

<i>Forest Characteristics</i>	<i>Response</i>
Forest Size	
Forest Location	
Forest Ownership	
Forest Species	
Forest Production	

PART 2: Forestry Business Model

This part collects information on the forestry business model, to understand the state of the art of the activities conducted, the value the forest provides, costs incurred and partnering stakeholders.

Forestry Business Model – to be filled in

Key partnerships	Key activities	Value propositions	Key beneficiaries / Customers	Governance
	Key resources	Key Services		
Cost structure		Revenue streams		

Guiding questions for part 2

BM Category	Questions
Value proposition	<p>What unique benefits or services does your forestry business offer to stakeholders?</p> <p>How do you differentiate your forestry products or services from those of competitors?</p> <p>What are the primary value drivers that attract customers to your forestry operations?</p>
Beneficiaries / customers	<p>Who are the primary beneficiaries of your forestry activities (e.g., timber industry, local communities, environmental conservation groups)?</p> <p>Who are your primary customers or target market segments for forestry products or services?</p>
Key activities	<p>What are the core activities involved in your forestry business model (e.g., forest management, timber harvesting, reforestation)?</p> <p>How do you integrate sustainable forestry practices into your key activities?</p>
Key Resources	<p>What are the essential resources required to support your forestry activities (e.g., land, timber inventory, equipment)?</p> <p>Do you rely on any external resources or partnerships to enhance your forestry operations?</p>
Key partnerships	<p>Do you rely on any partnerships to enhance your forestry operations?</p>
Governance	<p>Who owns the project? Who owns the land? Who makes decisions?</p>
Revenue	<p>What are the main sources of revenue for your forestry business (e.g., timber sales, eco-tourism, carbon credits)?</p>
Costs	<p>What are the primary cost components associated with your forestry operations (e.g., land acquisition, labor, equipment maintenance)?</p> <p>How do you manage and optimize costs to ensure the financial sustainability of your forestry business?</p> <p>Do you incur any certification costs/ or right to manage the land?</p>

PART 3: Soil health practices related to forestry activities

This part collects information on the implementation of forest activities in terms of soil health practices (SHP).

Knowledge & information on SHP

Q: How did you learn about SHPs?

Q: Did you have the requisite knowledge to make an informed decision at the time?

Q: Were there places that could inform you about SHPs?

Implementation of SHP

Q: Do you actively implement or have you implemented SHP?

Q: What type of practices have you implemented?

Q: What specific techniques or methods do you use to maintain or improve soil health?

Q: Please describe all SHP or Sustainable practices you are implementing

Q: How did you perceive the ease of implementation of SHP?

PART 4: Drivers & barriers - Factors influencing the implementation of soil health practices

This part helps understand the drivers and barriers influencing the implementation to more sustainable forest practices.

Drivers & barriers to implement SHP

Category	Sub-Category	Question (examples)
Environment	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversity)</i>	Do you consider environmental issues and the role of forestry important? Do these environmental issues play a role in your decision-making, and how?
	<i>Soil health</i>	Has the goal of improving soil health motivated you to adopt specific practices? If so, which ones?
	<i>Carbon Sequestration</i>	Is carbon sequestration a relevant or motivating factor in your land management strategy?
Economic	<i>Agronomic</i>	Did the financial aspect play a role in the decision, and how? Do you receive payments for introducing SHPs?
Social	<i>Society & community</i>	Were there other people that influenced you in adopting SHP? Such as local farmers, associations, agricultural advisors, or community groups? How important is peer learning or farmer-to-farmer exchange in your adoption process?
	<i>Workforce</i>	Have workforce-related factors (e.g. availability of labor, knowledge, training) helped or hindered your ability to implement new practices?
Institutional	<i>Public policy</i>	What is the role of policy considering SHPs? Are there policies that help you to introduce them, or the other way around? Are there any specific programs that supported you to introduce these practices? Are there any programs that inhibited you from introducing these practices?

PART 5: Impact of forestry practices - Observed outcomes of soil health interventions

This section aims to assess the impact of sustainable forestry practices across environmental, economic, social, and policy dimensions.

Knowledge & information on Impact

Q: What kind of activity influence your impact in terms of:

- Political & Legal
 - o Influence policy decision
- Economic
 - o Revenue generation
 - o Saving Costs / Saving costs of inaction
 - o Production costs (In / Decrease)
 - o Scalability
 - o Resource use
- Social
 - o Community engagement
 - o Employment opportunity
 - o Work safety
 - o Employment training
 - o Recreational activities (hunting, hiking, camp)
- Environment
 - o Soil
 - o Flora / Fauna
 - o Air
 - o Water
 - o GHG Emission
 - o Carbon sequestration
 - o Waste generation

Guiding questions for part 5

Category	Sub-Category	Question (examples)
Environment	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversity)</i>	<p>Have you perceived any visual environmental improvements and benefits in the forest since implementing Forestry practices?</p> <p>Did you observe any re-growth in indigenous species and a re-population of fauna?</p> <p>Any direct observable impacts on the land biodiversity?</p>
	<i>Soil health</i>	<p>How do you perceive these practices affecting soil health over time?</p> <p>Soil quality & fertility?</p> <p>Have you seen any improvement or deterioration in terms of flooding?</p> <p>Do the soils evacuate water easily?</p>
	<i>Carbon Sequestration</i>	<p>Do you measure carbon sequestration?</p> <p>If yes, how do you measure this?</p> <p>In what ways do you observe your soil health practices contribute to carbon sequestration?</p>
Economic	<i>Agronomic</i>	<p>How did you view the potential economic benefits to your forest when implementing more SHP ?</p> <p>What are the economic benefits or challenges associated with implementing more sustainable forestry practices?</p> <p>Have you experienced any changes in productivity, costs, or revenue by implementing certain forestry practices?</p> <p>Are these SHP scalable on total surface ? Do you need conventional forestry to be cost effective ?</p>
Social	<i>Society & community</i>	<p>Are there any forestry practices that have a direct impact on the surrounding community?</p> <p>Any changes in community engagement or support for forestry activities?</p>
	<i>Workforce</i>	<p>How do the forestry activities impact the work or conditions of foresters or farmers?</p>
Institutional	<i>Public policy</i>	<p>Have your practices contributed to institutional policies or regulations?</p>

PARTE 6: Carbon credits - Understanding the use of carbon credit mechanisms – if applicable

This section aims to explore the role of carbon credits and assess farmers' experiences, motivations, and challenges in engaging with the market.

Monitoring & Measurement

Q: Do you currently monitor or measure carbon sequestration on your land? If so, how?

Q: What types of indicators or methods do you use

Market participation

Q: Have you entered or attempted to enter the carbon credit market?

Q: What motivated your interest in participating in this market?

Q: Have you already experienced any benefits in participating in the market?

Processes & Challenges

Q: Are you working with any specific organization or program to measure carbon and sell credits?

Q: How does this process work in practice? What are the main steps and how long does it take?

Q: What challenges or barriers have you encountered in trying to join or benefit from the carbon market?

Q: Have you been able to sell any credits yet? If not, why?

8.2. Ex-post forestry assessment interview guide – Spanish version

PARTE 1: Introducción y contexto

Descripción de la organización

<i>Descripción de la organización</i>	<i>Respuesta</i>
Nombre Organización	
Tipo Organización	
Misión y organización de actividades	

Descripción del perfil

<i>Descripción del perfil</i>	<i>Respuesta</i>
Nombre	
Papel	
Actividades	
Formación / Experiencia forestal	

Características forestales

<i>Características forestales</i>	<i>Respuesta</i>
Tamaño del bosque / superficie arbolada	
Ubicación en el bosque / superficie arbolada	
Propiedad forestal	
Especies forestales	
Producción forestal	

PARTE 2: Modelo de negocio forestal

Esta parte recoge información sobre el modelo de negocio forestal, para comprender el estado de las actividades realizadas, el valor que aporta el bosque, los costes incurridos y las partes interesadas asociadas.

Modelo de Negocio Forestal – por completar

Asociaciones clave	Actividades principales	Propuestas de valor	Principales beneficiarios / clientes	Gobernanza
	Recursos clave	Servicios clave		
Estructura de costes		Flujos de ingresos		

Preguntas orientadoras para la parte 2

Categoría BM	Preguntas
Propuesta de valor	<p>¿Qué ventajas o servicios exclusivos ofrece su empresa forestal a las partes interesadas?</p> <p>¿Cómo diferencia sus productos o servicios forestales de los de la competencia?</p> <p>¿Cuáles son los principales factores de valor que atraen a los clientes a sus explotaciones forestales?</p>
Beneficiarios / clientes	<p>¿Quiénes son los principales beneficiarios de sus actividades forestales (por ejemplo, industria maderera, comunidades locales, grupos de conservación del medio ambiente)?</p> <p>¿Quiénes son sus principales clientes o segmentos del mercado objetivo de productos o servicios forestales?</p>
Actividades principales	<p>¿Cuáles son las actividades principales de su modelo de negocio forestal (por ejemplo, gestión forestal, tala de madera, reforestación)?</p> <p>¿Cómo integra las prácticas de silvicultura sostenible en sus principales actividades?</p>
Recursos clave	<p>¿Cuáles son los recursos esenciales necesarios para apoyar sus actividades forestales (por ejemplo, terrenos, inventario maderero, equipamiento)?</p> <p>¿Cuenta con recursos externos o asociaciones para mejorar sus operaciones forestales?</p>
Asociaciones clave	<p>¿Confía en alguna asociación para mejorar sus operaciones forestales?</p>
Gobernanza	<p>¿A quién pertenece el proyecto? ¿A quién pertenece el terreno?</p> <p>¿Quién toma las decisiones?</p>
Ingresos	<p>¿Cuáles son las principales fuentes de ingresos de su empresa forestal (por ejemplo, venta de madera, ecoturismo, créditos de carbono)?</p>
Costes	<p>¿Cuáles son los principales componentes de los costes asociados a sus operaciones forestales (por ejemplo, adquisición de tierras, mano de obra, mantenimiento de equipos)?</p> <p>¿Cómo gestiona y optimiza los costes para garantizar la sostenibilidad financiera de su empresa forestal?</p> <p>¿Incurrir en gastos de certificación/ o derecho a gestionar la tierra?</p>

PARTE 3: Practicas para la salud del suelo

Esta parte consiste en recopilar información sobre las actividades más específicas que el bosque lleva a cabo en términos de prácticas de salud del suelo (PSS).

Conocimiento e información sobre las Prácticas de Salud del Suelo

P: ¿Cómo se enteró de las PSS?

P: ¿Contaba con el conocimiento necesario para tomar una decisión informada en ese momento?

P: ¿Había lugares o fuentes que pudieran informarle sobre las PSS?

Implementación de las PSS

P: ¿Implementa activamente o ha implementado alguna vez PSS?

P: ¿Qué tipo de prácticas ha implementado?

P: ¿Qué técnicas o métodos específicos utiliza para mantener o mejorar la salud del suelo?

P: Por favor, describa todas las prácticas sostenibles o de salud del suelo que está implementando.

P: ¿Cómo percibió la facilidad de implementación de las PSS?

PARTE 4: Impulsores y barreras – Factores que influyen en la implementación de prácticas de salud del suelo

Esta parte ayuda a comprender los factores que impulsan o dificultan la implementación de prácticas forestales más sostenibles.

Impulsores y barreras para implementar Prácticas de Salud del Suelo (PSS)

Categoría	Subcategoría	Pregunta (ejemplos)
Medioambiente	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversidad)</i>	¿Considera importantes los aspectos medioambientales y el papel del sector forestal? ¿Estos aspectos medioambientales influyen en su toma de decisiones? ¿De qué manera?
	<i>Salud del suelo</i>	¿El objetivo de mejorar la salud del suelo le ha motivado a adoptar prácticas específicas? Si es así, ¿cuáles?
	<i>Captura de carbono</i>	¿La captura de carbono es un factor relevante o motivador en su estrategia de gestión del suelo o del bosque?
Económico	<i>Agronómica</i>	¿El aspecto financiero influyó en la decisión? ¿Cómo? ¿Recibe pagos por introducir prácticas de salud del suelo (PSS)?
Social	<i>Sociedad y comunidad</i>	¿Hubo otras personas que influyeron en su adopción de PSS? ¿Qué tan importante es el aprendizaje entre pares o el intercambio entre agricultores en su proceso de adopción?
	<i>Mano de obra</i>	¿Factores relacionados con la mano de obra han facilitado o dificultado la implementación de nuevas prácticas?
Institucional	<i>Política pública</i>	¿Cuál es el papel de las políticas públicas respecto a las PSS? ¿Existen políticas que le ayuden a introducir estas prácticas, o lo contrario? ¿Hay programas específicos que le hayan apoyado para introducir estas prácticas? ¿Existen programas que hayan dificultado la introducción de estas prácticas?

PARTE 5: Impacto de las prácticas forestales – Resultados observados de las intervenciones en salud del suelo

Esta sección tiene como objetivo evaluar el impacto de las prácticas forestales sostenibles en distintas dimensiones: medioambiental, económica, social y política.

Conocimiento e información sobre el impacto

P: ¿Qué tipo de actividad influye en su impacto en términos de:

- Político y legal
 - o Influencia en la toma de decisiones políticas
- Económico
 - o Generación de ingresos
 - o Ahorro de costes / Ahorro frente a la inacción
 - o Costes de producción (aumento / reducción)
 - o Escalabilidad
 - o Uso de recursos
- Social
 - o Participación comunitaria
 - o Oportunidades de empleo
 - o Seguridad laboral
 - o Formación profesional
 - o Actividades recreativas (caza, senderismo, acampada)
- Medioambiental
 - o Salud del suelo
 - o Flora / Fauna
 - o Calidad del aire
 - o Calidad del agua
 - o Emisiones de GEI
 - o Captura de carbono
 - o Generación de residuos

Guiding questions for part 5

Categoría	Subcategoría	Pregunta (ejemplos)
Medioambiente	<i>Flora, fauna (biodiversidad)</i>	¿Ha percibido mejoras y beneficios medioambientales visuales en el bosque desde la aplicación de las prácticas silvícolas? ¿Ha observado un rebrote de las especies autóctonas y una repoblación de la fauna?
	<i>Salud del suelo</i>	¿Cómo cree que estas prácticas afectan a la salud del suelo a lo largo del tiempo? ¿Calidad y fertilidad del suelo? ¿Ha observado alguna mejora o empeoramiento en términos de inundaciones? ¿Y en cuanto al suministro de agua? ¿Han tenido muchas sequías? ¿Los suelos evacúan el agua con facilidad?
	<i>Captura de carbono</i>	¿Mide la captura de carbono? En caso afirmativo, ¿cómo realiza esta medición? ¿De qué manera observa que sus prácticas de salud del suelo contribuyen a la captura de carbono?
Económico	<i>Agronómica</i>	¿Cómo percibió los posibles beneficios económicos para su bosque al implementar más prácticas de salud del suelo? ¿Cuáles son los beneficios o desafíos económicos asociados con la adopción de prácticas forestales más sostenibles? ¿Ha experimentado cambios en productividad, costes o ingresos al implementar ciertas prácticas forestales? ¿Estas prácticas de salud del suelo son escalables a toda la superficie?
Social	<i>Sociedad y comunidad</i>	¿Existen prácticas forestales que tengan un impacto directo en la comunidad local? ¿Ha habido cambios en el compromiso o apoyo de la comunidad hacia las actividades forestales?
	<i>Mano de obra</i>	¿Cómo impactan las actividades forestales en el trabajo o condiciones de los silvicultores o agricultores?
Institucional	<i>Política pública</i>	¿Sus prácticas han contribuido a políticas o regulaciones institucionales?

PARTE 6: Créditos de carbono – Comprender el uso de mecanismos de créditos de carbono (si aplica)

Esta sección tiene como objetivo explorar el papel de los créditos de carbono y evalúa.

Monitoreo y medición

P: ¿Actualmente monitorea o mide la captura de carbono en sus tierras? Si es así, ¿cómo lo hace?

P: ¿Qué tipos de indicadores o métodos utiliza?

Participación en el mercado

P: ¿Ha ingresado o intentado ingresar al mercado de créditos de carbono?

P: ¿Qué motivó su interés en participar en este mercado?

P: ¿Ha experimentado ya algún beneficio al participar en este mercado?

Procesos y desafíos

P: ¿Está trabajando con alguna organización o programa específico para medir el carbono y vender créditos?

P: ¿Cómo funciona este proceso en la práctica? ¿Cuáles son los pasos principales y cuánto tiempo requiere?

P: ¿Qué desafíos o barreras ha encontrado al intentar ingresar o beneficiarse del mercado de carbono?

P: ¿Ha logrado vender algún crédito hasta ahora? Si no, ¿por qué?

8.3. Consent form

Project title: Monetary valuation of soil ecosystem services and creation of initiatives to invest in soil health: setting a framework for the inclusion of soil health in business and in the policy making process- InBestSoil (Horizon Europe Project 101091099)

Project coordinator: Diego Soto Gómez, University of Vigo.

Work Package 4 - Task 4.3. : Ex post assessment of forestry business model : Helena Suarez, LGI Sustainable Innovation

About the project: InBestSoil main research question is: Can we maintain and restore soil health and resilience to climate change impacts by developing innovative business models and incentive tools based on the economic valuation of ecosystem services provided by soil? To this end, InBestSoil hypothesizes that translating the ecosystem services provided by healthy soils and the impacts of soil interventions into monetary values, and co-designing business models and incentives related to these values, will increase awareness of opportunities to invest in soil health, and thus establish new businesses to maintain and restore soil health in Europe. We will attempt to validate this hypothesis using lighthouses (LHs) and living laboratories (LLs) as hubs. We consider a LH as a place for the demonstration of long-term solutions, which are exemplary in their performance in terms of soil health improvement, and a LL as the collaboration between some research and innovation ecosystems, involving regional stakeholders in systemic research and co-design, to jointly improve the effectiveness of new practices on soil health.

Purpose of your participation: You are invited to be part of our research study on Ex post assessment of forestry business model as part of the InBestSoil project. You are asked to participate to an interview on forestry practices, soil health practices and business models.

Time of participation: The project lasts four years (from 2023 to 2026).

Risks and Benefits: Because of the innovative nature of the techniques being tried in the project, the results may not be as expected, including in terms of advices and proposition of innovant techniques and there is no guarantee or assurance that you will receive any benefit from this study. Your choice whether to participate in this study will not affect your participation in other InBestSoil events and activities.

Reimbursement: You will not receive any reimbursement as payment for your participation.

Rights: Your participation is voluntary, and you have the right to decline to participate and to remove your participation, samples, or data at any time with no consequences. You have the right to decline to answer certain questions. Your name and personal contact information will always be kept confidential, will never be made public, trackable or accessible, and you will never be identified or linked to the samples or data. You will always be the owner of the data and samples collected. You will be able to access the data by personal communication and/or report.

Use of data/samples: The collected materials and data will be part of studies that may be presented at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes of the InBestSoil project. Personal Data will be used only for administrative, operational, accounting, research and monitoring purposes that are necessary for the safe and reliable execution of InBestSoil, without affecting the individual's rights under the relevant laws.

Data Storage, Security, Retention, and Destruction: Data will be safely stored in a private InBestSoil Teams folder. The University of Cartagena protects this folder from viruses and data hacking, and performs regular backups. In the unlikely event of chance findings, you will be notified to decide whether you wish to delete your data. Personal Data will be retained until data derived from samples, surveys, questionnaires, or interviews are scientifically processed and published, and will be destroyed after a period of 18 months following publication. By default, Personal Data will be destroyed 36 months after the end of the InBestSoil.

Contact information: If you have any questions, concerns or complaints about this research, its procedures, risks and benefits, please contact the Project Coordinator (Dr. Diego Soto Gómez; disoto@uvigo.es; +34 660679251). Or Work Package 4 - Task 4.3. : Helena Suarez Groen, helena.suarezgroen@lgi.earth, LGI Sustainable Innovation.

Independent contact: If you are dissatisfied with the way this study is being conducted, or if you have any general concerns, complaints, or questions about the research or your rights as a participant, please contact Sabela González (R&D technician, not involved in the project), Universidade de Vigo (dir.inv.opi@uvigo.gal, +34 986 818639) to speak with someone independent of the research team.

Indicate Yes or No:

I give consent for registration of data resulting from this study to be used at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes: ___Yes ___No

I give consent for audio and/or videos resulting from this study to be used at scientific or professional meetings or published in scientific or professional journals for communication and dissemination purposes: ___Yes ___No

On default, your identity (name and contact data) will be retained anonymous and confidential, unless you give explicit consent to reveal your identity: __Yes

Signed, on duplicate, so that one copy of this signed and dated consent form is for you to keep.

NAME:

ORGANIZATION:

DATE:

SIGNATURE

8.4. Drivers and Barriers to implementing soil health related forestry practices - synthesis

8.4.1. Drivers and barriers to LH1

Drivers to LH1

Low cost of implementation

- Initial setup of rotational grazing systems is relatively inexpensive
- Farmers reported significant reductions in input costs, particularly in water and feed, up to 80% savings in some cases

Rapid visibility of benefits

- Positive ecological changes, such as improved soil health and vegetation recovery, are often noticeable within a short time
- These "quick wins" reinforce continued use and refinement of holistic methods

Desire for long-term land viability

- Many farmers were motivated by the realization that, without change, their land would continue to degrade, reducing both productivity and profitability
- Holistic management offers a path to reversing this decline

Enhanced resilience to drought and climate stress

- La Dehesa faces a range of soil health challenges due to severe weather conditions that must be addressed to sustain land productivity:
 - No vegetation growth all year round
 - No humidity and temperature conditions for the necessary microbiological activity
 - Continuous land degradation
- Improved soil structure and water retention through rotational grazing increases landscape-level resilience, a critical advantage in the arid Dehesa environment

Ecosystem regeneration outcomes

- Farmers observed natural regeneration of native plant species, improved biodiversity, and higher animal fertility

Deeper understanding of land systems

- Holistic management fosters a systems-based approach, emphasizing the interconnectedness between soil, animals, vegetation, and ecological processes

- For many farmers, this approach transformed how they understood and related to their land

Barriers to LH1

Despite the benefits there are also clear challenge that hinder the wider adoption of these practices.

Labour intensity and complexity

- Rotational grazing requires regular planning and movement of livestock, which is often seen as labour-intensive—especially for larger farms

Perceived loss of productivity

- Leaving parts of the land to rest contradicts conventional practices and can feel like a reduction in usable pasture
- Some farmers worry about short-term declines in output, even though long-term benefits are well-documented

Resistance to change

- Older or traditionally trained farmers may be reluctant to adopt new practices
- Shifting to holistic management often requires a mindset shift, trust in ecological processes, and comfort with adaptive learning
- Interestingly, most interviewed farmers came from non-agricultural sectors, which made them more open to innovation

Consistency and commitment requirements

- Soil health improvements depend on regular monitoring, planning, and adaptation, these practices that require time and long-term commitment
- For newcomers practitioners, this can be difficult to sustain without peer support

Limited access to training and support networks

- A lack of formal training resources and limited exposure to successful case studies can slow adoption
- However, peer networks and regenerative farming communities have played a growing role in overcoming this barrier

8.4.2. Drivers and barriers to LH6

Drivers to LH6

In the LH6 context, several factors contribute to their implementation of soil health practices, particularly in state-owned and research-driven forests. These drivers

reflect a mix of policy requirements, ecological awareness, and social accountability:

Regulatory compliance

- State forests are mandated to follow environmental guidelines and certification standards (e.g. FSC, PEFC), which require specific soil management actions

Social pressure and public accountability

- Latvian forests face a range of soil health challenges that must be addressed to sustain long-term forestry productivity:
 - Diverse soil organic matter content
 - Unbalanced soil nutrient content
 - Soil acidification
 - Soil erosion on slopes
- NGOs and civil society increasingly scrutinize public land management practices, pushing for higher environmental performance, particularly in sensitive forest ecosystems
- State-owned forests must set an example for private forest owners and respond to public expectations for sustainable practices

Improved forest productivity and resilience

- SHP contribute to reduced erosion, better water retention, and nutrient stability, which in turn support healthier and faster-growing trees
- Recognized as a way to enhance long-term timber yield and site sustainability, particularly in erosion-prone or degraded areas

Research and innovation leadership

- SILAVA and other research institutions are motivated to trial new soil monitoring tools and adaptive practices as part of ongoing ecological research
- Experimental plots help validate SHP impacts and offer demonstration value for wider forestry audiences

Technological innovations

- The use of drones in research plots allows for the early detection of localized damage during planting or interventions
- The ability to pinpoint and address problems precisely reduces overall impact and enhances the strategic application of SHP

Barriers to LH6

Despite growing interest and ongoing research into soil health practices across Latvian forests, significant structural and economic barriers continue to hinder their

widespread implementation across state-owned, research-managed, and privately held forest landscapes.

Labour shortages

- Forestry work remains physically demanding, and Latvia is experiencing a decline in new generation workforce
- Staffing limitations hinder consistent field monitoring and adaptive intervention

Cost of implementation

- SHP often involve added expenses for soil analysis, equipment, or reduced short-term productivity
- Private forest owners frequently lack the economic margin to invest in practices that don't yield immediate returns

Limited funding for research forests

- Research institutions often operate on project-based grants, limiting the scalability of SHP beyond controlled experimental settings
- Short funding cycles constrain the ability to demonstrate long-term soil impacts

Lack of commercial incentives in private forestry

- Timber markets typically reward volume and quality, not soil stewardship
- Certification programs remain underutilized due to high entry costs and administrative demands
- In both public and private contexts, timber production, pest control, and infrastructure maintenance often take precedence over soil-focused actions.

Absence of clear technical guidelines

- Private forest owners often lack access to site-specific SHP recommendations or training.
- Variability in soil types, terrain, and forest composition adds complexity to standardization.

8.5. Ex-post forestry impact assessments - synthesis

8.5.1. LH1 ex-post agroforestry impact assessment

Social impact

Society and culture

The shift toward regenerative practices in the Dehesa represents more than just a change in forestry and land management, it marks a generational transformation. Many of the farmers leading this transition do not come from traditional agricultural backgrounds; instead, they bring knowledge and experience from other sectors, coupled with a strong willingness to innovate and experiment. Their fresh perspectives have contributed to the emergence of a vibrant local network focused on holistic management within silvopastoral systems. This community is grounded in a deep care for the land and a commitment to peer-to-peer learning. Initiatives such as AleJAB have played a key role in fostering this culture of shared knowledge and collective experimentation, creating a space where successes, challenges, and techniques are openly exchanged and continuously refined.

Forestry workers

The transition to regenerative agroforestry is also reshaping the role of forestry and agricultural workers. Instead of labour focused on extraction, such as intensive grazing or maintenance of degraded land, work is now more oriented around holistic management, which prioritises the ecological conditions of the landscape.

Economic impact

The economic benefits of regenerative farming in the Dehesa are quickly apparent to farmers. Many highlighted the low initial investment required to implement rotational grazing, often needing nothing more than a wire and a few poles to establish grazing zones. In addition, reductions in feed and animal supplement use have led to substantial cost savings over time.

Farmers are also diversifying their income streams, combining livestock production with olive oil and, in some cases, wool.

Environmental impact

Soil health

One of the most significant impacts is the restoration of degraded soils. Through the silvopastoral systems including practices like rotational grazing and grass finishing, farmers promote the natural restoration of soil health. Hoof action creates small indentations that improve water infiltration and retention, crucial in the Dehesa's dry and rocky conditions.

Biodiversity

Regenerative agroforestry supports above and below ground biodiversity. As rotational grazing creates rest periods, soil, grass and plant species can recover and expand. The integration of livestock within tree systems, such as olive groves

also strengthens multispecies interaction, supports pollinators and builds the ecological network, eventually improving animal health.

Animal well-being

Farmers also reported positive outcomes for animal health. Improved pasture quality and rotational systems led to lower disease incidence and better animal fertility. Specifically plant biodiversity also improves the nutritional value of animal feed. Specifically rotational grazing also ensure cows eat plants at specific moments when they are at their most nutritious stage. This targeted approach balances livestock feeding needs with plant regeneration and biodiversity enhancement.

Carbon sequestration

While still in early stages, carbon monitoring is emerging as a complementary component of regenerative agriculture in the Dehesa. Improvements in soil health through practices like rotational grazing and land restoration contribute to enhanced carbon sequestration. Although monetizing this carbon sequestration to carbon credits is still limited, these steps still highlight the potential of silvopastoral systems to deliver both environmental benefits and future economic opportunities.

Institutional / legal impact

LH1 illustrates how farmer-led networks can drive ecological innovation and peer-to-peer learning in agroforestry. These grassroots initiatives strengthen local governance but also expose gaps in formal policy support, highlighting the need for more adaptive and enabling institutional frameworks for regenerative land management.

8.5.2. LH6 ex-post forestry impact assessment

Social impact

Society and Culture

Forestry and forest access in Latvia bring significant positive social impacts. Both state and privately owned forests contribute to community well-being by enabling a wide range of recreational and cultural activities, including hiking, biking, and foraging for berries and mushrooms—activities deeply embedded in Latvian tradition. These practices promote not only physical health and mental well-being but also reinforce cultural heritage. Educational programs in many forests further enhance community engagement by educating people about sustainable practices and the importance of conservation.

However, these benefits are not without trade-offs. Increased public access can introduce ecological risks:

- Allergies from certain plant species or tree pollen
- Tick-borne diseases posing a health threat to visitors

- Spread of invasive species facilitated by informal road creation and foot traffic
- Litter and microplastic contamination, particularly in high-use areas

These "ecosystem dis-services" underscore the need for responsible forest planning and visitor management, balancing open access with conservation.

Forestry workers

The physical demands of forestry interventions significantly impact the attractiveness of the job, leading to a shortage of labour in the sector. The strenuous and challenging nature of forestry work discourages many potential workers, exacerbating the labour shortage. This not only affects the implementation of sustainable practices, such as those requiring manual monitoring or adaptive responses, but also places limits on the scale and consistency of interventions

Economic impact

Forestry interventions have a significant economic impact, offering both opportunities and challenges. On one hand, these interventions can create substantial business opportunities, particularly in timber production, recreational services, and innovative forestry products. These activities can generate considerable revenue and support local economies and businesses and create job opportunities.

However there is a significant cost associated to forestry interventions, especially with advanced machinery and technology. Research-driven forestry projects, while essential for innovation and sustainable practices, often do not generate immediate profit, making it difficult to secure long-term funding and sustain projects over extended periods.

Environmental impact

Soil Health

Forestry activities, the use of machinery, and public access can significantly impact soil health within forests. The heavy machinery used for logging and other forestry operations can compact the soil, reducing its porosity and ability to retain water, which negatively affects root growth and soil microorganisms.

Public access, especially through hiking and biking trails, can lead to soil erosion, and off-road vehicle use can disturb the soil structure, disrupt plant roots, and lead to the loss of nutrient-rich topsoil.

Forest visitors moreover, often leave behind litter, including plastics that degrade into microplastics, which infiltrate the soil and water systems, further disrupting soil health and harming plant and animal life.

While the active implementation of Soil Health Practices is still limited, research on these practices and innovative techniques presents significant opportunities to enhance soil health within forests. This research contributes to a deeper understanding of soil ecosystems and informs the development of sustainable

forestry management practices that prioritize soil health. By exploring new methods and technologies, researchers can identify effective strategies to preserve and improve soil quality, ultimately creating faster growing forests and promoting healthier forest ecosystems and sustainable forestry practices.

Biodiversity

Monoculture stands of pine, spruce, and birch dominate commercial forestry landscapes. While efficient for production, such uniformity reduces habitat diversity, threatening native species and ecological resilience. Biodiversity loss is a common consequence of intensive forestry operations, especially where undergrowth is cleared or soil layers are disturbed.

Research forests and certified state-owned lands attempt to counterbalance this through:

- Mixed-species planting
- Habitat retention practices
- Conservation zones within production areas

Carbon sequestration

Latvian forests serve as carbon sinks, with forest soils and biomass capturing and storing atmospheric CO₂. However, business-oriented practices, particularly clear-cutting and frequent harvesting, can deplete this function over time if not offset by effective regeneration.

Conversely, research and public forest interventions are increasingly aligned with climate goals. By focusing on soil carbon monitoring, long-term biomass tracking, and replanting strategies, LH6 and similar sites support Latvia's contribution to EU carbon neutrality targets.

Carbon sequestration efforts remain in early stages, and while monetization through carbon credit schemes is limited, growing awareness of forests' climate value is influencing both policy and practice.

Institutional / legal impact

LH6 contributes to institutional forestry standards in Latvia through its integration with SILAVA and state forest governance. Its research informs national guidelines, supports certification compliance, and strengthens the link between science and regulatory frameworks in public forest management.

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